

ECOBULK

Circular Approach for Eco-Composite Bulky Product

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Report on Design Circular framework setting

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

1 Summary	8
2 Introduction	8
2.1 Towards the circular economic model	8
2.2 Design for circularity	10
2.3 Design Framework workshop and methodology	13
2.4 Design solutions and main challenges	1
3 Composite recovery in the automotive industry	7
3.1 Recovery perspective	7
3.1.1 Design	7
3.1.2 Present situation	7
3.1.3 Tools & machines	7
3.1.4 Changes in type of materials	8
3.1.5 Other comments	8
3.2 Main challenges	8
3.3 Design solutions	9
3.4 Recovery strategies	11
4 Composite recovery in the furniture industry	12
4.1 Recovery perspective	12
4.1.1 Design	12
4.1.2 Present situation	13
4.1.3 Tools & machines	13
4.1.4 Changes in type of materials	14
4.1.5 Other comments	14
4.2 Main challenges	15
4.3 Design solutions	15
4.4 Recovery strategies	17
5 Composite recovery in the building industry	19
5.1 Recovery perspective	19
5.1.1 Design	19
5.1.2 Present situation	19
5.1.3 Tools & machines	21
5.1.4 Changes in type of materials	24
5.1.5 Other comments	26
5.2 Main challenges	27
5.3 Design solutions	28
5.4 Recovery strategies	29
6 Extra information. Non-woven recovery.	31
6.1 Recovery perspective	31
6.1.1 Design	31
6.1.2 Present situation	31
6.1.3 Tools & machines	31
6.1.4 Changes in type of materials	33
6.1.5 Other comments	33
7 Extra information. Additional comments from the questionnaire	33
8 Annex I. Detailed workshop results	1

Glossary of key terms:

Table 1 Glossary

Term	Description
Business model	An organisation chosen system of decisions and activities that determines how it creates, delivers and captures value over time.
Circular economy	A circular economy entails decoupling economic activity from the consumption of finite resource and designing waste and pollution out of the system. It aims to keep products and materials in use for as long as possible, extract the maximum value from them whilst in use, then recover and regenerate products and materials at the end of each service life ¹ . A circular economy should build economic and social capital and regenerate natural systems.
Composite materials	A composite material is composed of at least two materials, which combine to give properties superior to those of the individual constituents. They typically result in lighter, stronger, more durable solutions compared to traditional materials ² .
Disposal	Any operation which is not recovery, even where the operation has a secondary consequence, the reclamation of substances or energy ⁵ .
Prevention	Measures taken before a substance, material or product has become waste that reduce the quantity of waste, the adverse impacts of the generated waste on environment and human health and the content of harmful substances in materials and products ⁵ .
Recovery	Any operation the principal result of which is waste serving a useful purpose by replacing other materials which would otherwise have been used to fulfil a particular function, or waste being prepared to fulfil that function in the plant or wider economy ⁶ .

¹ Adopted from The Ellen Macarthur Foundation and the UKs Waste Resources Action Programme

² Taken from Composites UK

Term	Description
Recycling	Any recovery operation by which waste materials are reprocessed into products, materials or substances whether for the original or other purposes. It includes the reprocessing of organic material but does not include energy recovery and the reprocessing into materials that are to be used as fuels or for backfilling operations ⁶ .
Remanufacturing	Return a used product to at least its original performance with a warranty that is equivalent to or better than that of the newly manufactured product ³ .
Repair	Return a faulty or broken product, component or material back to a usable state. A repair may use remanufactured or reconditioned parts ⁴ .
Reuse	Any operation by which products or components that are not waste are used again for the same purpose for which they were conceived ⁶ .
Systems thinking	A holistic approach to understanding how different parts of a system can influence one another and the relationship of the system to the parts over time ⁴ .
Waste	Any substance or object which the holder discards or intends or is required to discard ⁵ .
Waste hierarchy	The priority order in waste prevention and management: prevention, reuse, recycling, recover, disposal ⁵ .
Obsolescence	The product use cycle ends, a product becomes obsolete, when the product is no longer considered useful or significant by its users.

³ Taken from BS 8887-2:2009 Design for manufacture, assembly, disassembly and end-of-life processing. Terms and definitions

⁴ Taken from BS 8001:2017, framework for implementing the principles of the circular economy in organizations- Guide

⁵ Taken from the EU Waste Framework Directive

Term	Description
Product lifetime	Starts when the product is released after manufacturing and ends when the product is obsolete beyond recovery at product level. (den Hollander, 2017)
Product use cycle	Starts after manufacturing or recovery and ends when the product becomes obsolete.
Product integrity	To ensure product integrity, focus on the quality fundamentals with distinct rigor and discipline is necessary. The design intent and process capability must be established early in the product lifecycle. Production teams should manufacture the as designed product in a repeatable and an affordable way. Capgemini can help product companies to achieve these goals.
Product	Product is a system made available for consumer use; it is anything that can be offered to a market to satisfy the desire or need of a customer.

1 Summary

ECOBULK focuses on re-using, upgrading, refurbishing, and recycling composite products if possible, profitable, sustainable and appealing. ECOBULK tries to reach a circular model by shifting the pre-conceptions of design, manufacturing, logistics and customer behaviour, benefits for the environment can be created as well as for the society and the economy, while offering business opportunities to participants along the entire value chain.

This deliverable will set design requirements that make products more easily repairable and longer-lasting. Besides, it will ensure that the materials and components of a product can be more easily re-used, refurbished and recycled, and finally, it will ensure that products are free of hazardous or problematic substances, which can hamper re-use or recycling efforts.

To do so, different workshops were organized by ITENE and TUDelft. The different workshops were carried out during the General Assembly between the 13th and 14th of June 2018 in Koblenz (Germany).

More than 20 participants gave their inputs about challenges and design solutions for the different recovery strategies explained.

After this workshop, a questionnaire was sent to the partners, which results are exposed in this deliverable.

Along this deliverable, the reader can also find all the results gathered and analysed. These results set the basis for the redesign work to be done for the different products of the three sectors (automotive, furniture and building) in the following tasks.

2 Introduction

2.1 Towards the circular economic model

The concept of circular economy looks beyond the current linear industrial models of “take, make, and dispose”, and instead aims to redefine products and services to design waste out, while also minimizing negative impacts of a linear economy. With scarce resources and an ever-increasing global population, the idea behind circular economy principles is to build long-term resilience, generate business and economic opportunities, and provide environmental and societal benefits.

Such an economy is based on a few simple principles, as shown in Figure 1-1. First, at its core, a circular economy aims to design out waste. Waste does not exist: products are

designed and optimized for a cycle of disassembly and reuse. These tight component and product cycles define the circular economy and set it apart from disposal and even recycling, where large amounts of embedded energy and labour are lost. Second, circularity introduces a strict differentiation between consumable and durable components of a product. Unlike today, consumables in the circular economy are largely made of biological ingredients or 'nutrients' that are at least non-toxic and possibly even beneficial, and can safely be returned to the biosphere, either directly or in a cascade of consecutive uses. Durables such as engines or computers, on the other hand, are made of technical nutrients unsuitable for the biosphere, such as metals and most plastics. These are designed from the start for reuse, and products subject to rapid technological advance are designed for upgrade. Third, the energy required to fuel this cycle should be renewable by nature, again to decrease resource dependence and increase systems resilience (to oil shocks, for example)⁶.

¹ Hunting and fishing

² Can take both postharvest and postconsumer waste as an input

Figure 1-1. The circular economy—an industrial system that is restorative by design

⁶ World Economic Forum. Web: <http://reports.weforum.org/toward-the-circular-economy-accelerating-the-scale-up-across-global-supply-chains/from-linear-to-circular-accelerating-a-proven-concept/#view/fn-12>

(Source: Ellen MacArthur Foundation circular economy team drawing from Braungart & McDonough and Cradle to Cradle (C2C))

The two *Towards the Circular Economy* reports published by the Ellen MacArthur Foundation provide ample evidence that circularity has started to make inroads into the linear economy and has moved beyond proof of concept. A number of businesses are already thriving on it. Innovative products and contracts designed for the circular economy are already available in a variety of forms—from innovative designs of daily materials and products (e.g. biodegradable food packaging and easy-to-disassemble office printers) to pay-per-use contracts (for tyres for instance). Demonstrably, these examples have in common that they have focused on optimizing total systems performance rather than that of a single component.

2.2 Design for circularity

ECOBULK's circular economy model will create opportunities within the three sectors (automotive, furniture and building) by addressing and applying the waste hierarchy of the Waste Framework Directive (2008/98/EC).

Figure 1-2. Waste hierarchy related to ECOBULK circular strategies

This hierarchy matches with the circular design strategies followed to create the workshop, and they are the strategies set for the "Design for the Circularity" by Ellen MacArthur Foundation. The strategies are:

- a) **Reuse.** The use of a product again for the same purpose in its original form or with little enhancement or change. Reuse has the potential to solve the resource challenge by extending the service life of the products, reducing the waste stream and avoiding energy production and raw materials extraction.

Reuse is the tightest loop in the Circular Economy diagram. It saves resources by keeping existing products in use for longer. There are two types of reuse:

- Service-life extension. It is the simple redistribution of existing, preowned products to new users.
- Service-life intensification. It is based on the use of a single product, by many users, within short periods of time.

→ Design aspects to take into account to improve the chances of reuse:

- Durability of materials
- Ease of maintenance and repair
- Standardization, compatibility and adaptability
- Product attachment and trust

- b) **Repair.** A process of returning a product to good working condition by replacing or repairing major components that are faulty or close to failure and making 'cosmetic' changes to update the appearance of a product. Repair helps to solve the resource challenge by increasing the lifespan of the products, thus reducing the need for new resources.

Any technical product is in danger of breaking. To pick up the principle of reuse and to keep products as long as possible in use, we need to repair them. There are two main ways:

- Repair by a company (providing a repair service to the customers, sale of spare parts or providing market distinctions by the products being easy to repair by the customer).
- Repair by the customers (easy access, simple, modular structure of the product, no critical conditions should appear during the maintenance).

- c) **Remanufacture.** A process of disassembly and recovery at the subassembly or component level. Functioning, reusable parts are taken out of a used product and rebuilt into a new one. This process includes quality assurance and potential enhancements or changes to the components. Remanufacture keeps the added

value of the products saving resources and preventing mobilizing of new resources.

There are a number of strategies and concrete bits of advice that, in most cases, will facilitate and favour remanufacturing. These strategies are, for instance, documentation (adding an identifier to the product), diagnostic tools (to clarify what has to be done to the product), strong materials (multiple lifecycles), possibility of upgrading, modularization and product structure (avoiding cross-dependence between modules), cleaning (make it easy to clean), demounting (make it easy to demount), standards (use standardized elements and measures) or dimensions (adding extra material on surfaces) among others, but always taking into account that at the very end after a number of lifecycles, every product will end up in recycling, incineration or landfill. So, even if you aim for remanufacturing, you should also think about recycling.

- d) **Recycling.** A process of recovering materials for the original purpose or for other purposes, excluding energy recovery⁷. Recycling destroys the value of the product and requires energy, which makes it the last option for the Circular Economy. However, the importance of the recycling is significant as it keeps the materials in use and reduces the waste streams.

Recycling represents the last and crucial approach. This means that recycling has to be considered for all other approaches as well, since there will always be waste at the end which has to be minimised.

We have to understand that the Circular Economy requires many changes in the society and remember that this economy does not necessarily save energy and GHG emissions but leads to new business models, products and manufacturing processes that save energy and resources.

The European Commission adopted an ambitious **Circular Economy Package, which includes measures that will help** stimulate Europe's transition towards a circular economy, boost global competitiveness, foster sustainable economic growth and generate new jobs⁸. Therefore, the aim of ECOBULK's circular design approach is to deliver long-lasting and modular products that will be easy to upgrade, refurbish and

⁷ This definition is in line with Article 3(7) of Directive 94/62/ EC. This article additionally states that recycling includes organic recycling.

⁸ EU Action Plan for the Circular Economy. Web: http://ec.europa.eu/environment/circular-economy/index_en.htm

reuse, to be aligned with Europe's new regulations and to start building this mentioned transition.

2.3 Design Strategy Framework

The workshops this report build on the design strategy framework described in Ecobulk deliverable report D2.2: *Design strategies and tools, V1*. This paragraph gives a short introduction to circular product design strategies for composite products and the framework used to develop and analyse workshop materials.

2.3.1 Design strategies

Three design approaches can be identified to reduce the input (resources) and output (waste & emission) of a system: narrowing, slowing or closing the flow of resources through the system. Narrowing refers to using less materials, which is commonplace in product design as it results in direct cost reduction. A Lightweight design approach reduces both materials in the manufacturing stage and fuel consumption in the use phase, especially in transport applications. Slowing down the flow refers to keeping products in use for longer. Longevity of products & components is the goal of design for product integrity, compromising three design approaches: a long product lifetime, product life extension or recovery of the product at the end of its use cycle (den Hollander, 2018). Closing resource loops is the domain of recycling, where materials are reprocessed from obsolete products into raw materials ready for a next lifecycle.

Long lifetime is enabled by design for long use and reuse. For long use, the product life cycle is as long as the use cycle. Reuse aims to increase the number of use cycles within a single product lifecycle, for example by sharing.

Extended use is enabled by actions prolonging the product life, like maintenance, repair and upgrading. Addressing these in the initial design makes the operations later in the lifecycle easier and cost effective.

Product recovery returns obsolete products or parts thereof to working condition, returning products that risk to be lost to the economy.

Recycling recovers resources at a material level, thereby closing the loop. When the product or its components cannot be recovered anymore, recycling can return the materials to resources for new products. As all products will become obsolete one day, design for recycling is considered essential for all products.

Circular product design				
Design for product integrity				Design for recycling
Resources	Products and components			Materials
Approach	Long lifetime	Extended use	Product recovery	Recycling
Strategies	Long use	Maintenance & repair	Refurbishment	Composite recycling
	Reuse	Upgrading	Remanufacturing	Materials recycling

Table 1-1 Design approaches and strategies categorisation, based on (den Hollander, Bakker, & Hultink, 2017)

It is important to realise that these strategies do not work isolated, the system in which they are applied has to be regarded as well. A design strategy in itself will not make recovery happen. For example, refurbishment implies a long product (or component) lifetime which must be addressed; refurbishment is not interesting if the resulting product does not comply to new technical or functional demands.

Design strategies can pose multiple and sometimes conflicting demands on the product design. Therefore it is important to consider the desired recovery process and stakeholder in the design stage, as well as developing scenarios to anticipate future changes. The measures taken to increase a product's durability or other adjustments made must be weighed against the envisioned benefits. Additional resources used in the initial production must be worth the additional lifetime, use, recovery and recycling benefits.

Product design integrates requirements from (circular) business models and technological design aspects. The business model directs the product lifecycle; what kind of interventions will be done. When and which incentives are in place. A design strategy serves to bridge the gap to product design.

2.3.2 Design principles

During its lifetime, a product encounters many processes and stakeholders. In a circular economy, the number is likely to grow. It is important to gather knowledge about these processes and stakeholders and to translate these into technological aspects to include in the product design.

As specific technical aspects are product and context specific, providing universally applicable technological demands is impossible. Therefore a list generically applicable design principles is used. Generalising these principles has the benefit of widening applicability to a large group of products and identifying similarities between

technological design aspects. The design principles can be used to derive product specific design guidelines.

The set of principles proposed here builds on the *circular product design framework* (den Hollander, 2018). All design principles support multiple design strategies and are often interconnected. The workshops are used to explore relations between circular design strategies and principles in the context of composite products. Below, definitions are given for the design principles. For an elaborate description, refer to Ecobulk deliverable report D2.2 "Design strategies and tools, first version", published simultaneously with this report.

Design principle	Definition
Dis- & reassembly	Facilitate demounting of components in a non-destructive way
Modularity	The product is subdivided in functional units which operate largely independent from each other. Use of (functional) modules within a larger frame provides benefits in all lifecycle stages (Baldwin, 1999)
Identification	"Identification utilizes engraving, labelling or marking for quick location of parts or assemblies upon which preventive or corrective maintenance may have to be performed." (Moss, 1985)
Interchangeability	Enables easy exchange of components within an assembly. A feature that greatly benefits efficient lifetime extension and product recovery interventions.
Material Selection	Selecting the material that is best suited to the design requirements of the product under consideration (den Hollander, 2017)
Surface treatment selection	A surface treatment must be selected such, that it is "best suited to the design requirements of the product under consideration" ¹¹
Sorting facilitation	Designing of materials taking into account the sorting stage so that the initial design does not jeopardise this process.
Malfunction annunciation	Measures taken in the design to facilitate evaluation of product (structural) quality and fault isolation
Structural design	Utilizes the freedom of fibre composition and orientation within the material, having an effect on all lifecycle stages
Fastener & connection selection	Selection taking the envisioned lifetime extension and product recovery as well as material recycling processes into account
Documentation	Information about the design, materials, dimensions etc. enables multiple use cycles and proper end of life processing (recycling).
Planning	Planning is an important activity in the design of circular products. Timing, operations and incentives for future product interventions can be evaluated and anticipated for in the design.
Simplify	Reducing number and complexity of the product and its parts
Adaptability	Updating allows a product to keep performing the functions it was originally designed for in a changing environment whereas upgrading enhances the functionality of a product.
New business model	A business model that is better suited to operate with the product in a circular economy

Standardisation	Enforcing the commonly used paers and assemblies to generally accepted design standards of functional design attributes. ⁹
EU regulations	Although this is not directly a design solution, there is a need of updating the regulation across Europe.

2.4 Design workshop and methodology

2.4.1 Methodology

Product design is an iterative process wherein different aspects of the product have to be considered and reviewed. Iterations are needed because the aspects mutually influence each other. Within Ecobulk, we have the opportunity to involve experts from all fields, so a series of design activities focused on these aspects is proposed. In a series of successive design steps with each a distinct focus, the demonstrator design is refined. The design is done by the manufacturing/design partners and each step includes one or more project partners active in the respective knowledge area. For example, the materials evaluation and selection methods from Granta can be applied the materials focus.

For the final product, these focus areas cannot be seen separately and have to be integrated. In this integration step, the insights are used to create a final design proposal. The design process can have an iterative nature, with manufacturers assessing their progress and finetuning their work.

It is proposed to present all design concepts at the General Assembly, so all project partners can view the work and provide their ideas or questions.

Once the design is finished, it needs to be detailed for production.

Goal	Ecobulk action	Partners
Product definition	Baseline report	OEMs, Granta, TUDelft
Explore challenges & opportunities	Workshop & questionnaire	ITENE, TUDelft, participants
	Evaluate results	ITENE, TUDelft
Generic redesign	Design assignment 1	TUDelft, OEMs
Redesign: Business focus	Design assignment 2	TUDelft, OEMs, Oakdene Hollins
Redesign: Recovery	Design assignment 3	OEMs, Lipor, Belver, Tomra
Redesign: Materials	Design assignment 4	OEMs, Granta

⁹ Moss, M. A. (1985). *Designing for Minimal Maintenance Expense: The Practical Application Application of Reliability and Maintainability*. New York: Marcel Dekker.

Design integration	Concept selection	OEMs, Itene
	Poster presentation	OEMs
Finalise (detailing for productin)	Proceed to demo development	OEMs

This deliverable describes design progress until M18. A diagram to make the steps more clearly visible is seen in Figure 3:

Figure 3. Design process diagram

The following information details which partners will be involved in each part of the design process, as well as the tools and inputs needed and the expected outputs.

Business model strategies

- Tools: Business model and design strategies, semi structured interview, described in D2.2, Chapter 6
- Involved: Oakdene Hollins, TU Delft and individual OEMs
- Input: Circular principles and mindsets, evaluation format for current demonstrator design, inspirational examples
- Output: Challenges and opportunities for circular product and service design within Ecobulk
- Feedback on: Viability and circularity of envisioned business model

Recovery

- Tools: format to be detailed, potentially based on tools presented in the Circular Design guide presented by IDEO and Ellen MacEcrthur Foundation (for example the Disassembly worksheet, design checklists (for specific recovery mode, eg. Reman), part planning workshop)
- Involved: product and material recovery partners, Lipor, Belver, Tomra and OEMs
- Input: provisional design, current product sample, recovery actions & insights by EoL partners
- Output: Design improvements for specific recovery processes
- Feedback on: design, use of fasteners, actions etc (EoL facilitators)

Materials & manufacturing

- Tools: Materials and manufacturing selection tools developed by Granta, described in D2.3
- Involve: Granta and individual OEMs
- Input: Product and manufacturing criteria (OEMs)
- Output: materials and manufacturing process selection
- Feedback on: Use of (composite) materials, selection criteria

Concept selection

- Tool: format to be detailed, potentially based on tools presented in the Circular Design guide presented by IDEO and Ellen MacArthur Foundation (for example the Concept selection worksheet)
- Involved: Itene and OEMs
- Input: concept designs made over the past months
- Output: concept selection
- Feedback on: selection and match between concept and proposed recovery option (pointers for further detail design)

Further details about all the design process and strategies can be found along D2.2. "Design strategies and tools".

2.4.2 Design Framework Workshop

The workshop of design for circularity was performed during the GA in Koblenz, Germany. TUDelft and ITENE organized a set of workshops focused on each of the three industrial sectors – automotive, construction and furniture. In the field of circular economy, the

design focuses on keeping a product that has minimal impact on the environment and high economic value in circulation for as long as possible. This implies that the products should no longer have a cycle with a beginning, middle, and end but to come a part of a holistic closed loop. Materials were developed specifically for this workshop, building on the design strategy framework.

The workshops were organized around the specific pilot products from the three targeted markets (Table 2). The upholstered bed and the pillars outdoors were not analysed due to lack of resources; however, conclusions can be extrapolated from the other products in each sector, generating the following three general design options:

- Furniture: design for recovery with particle board materials
- Building: design for recovery with thermoplastic extrusion, plywood & OSB
- Automotive: design for recovery with thermoplastic injection moulded materials

Table 2. Specific pilot products from the three targeted markets

Sector	Reference Product(s)
Automotive	Fascia Central Console
	Safety belt brackets
	Trim for central panel
	Central Console Cowlings
Furniture	Upholstered bed
	Bookcase
Building	OSB structural panel
	plywood structural panel
	Panel
	Pillars outdoor

For each sector, people participating were divided in 3 or 4 groups (depending on the sector). Groups were formed by multi-disciplinary experts who applied a methodology designed to stimulate the design for recovery, the thinking of material value and subsequent product lifecycles. Each group consisted of both manufacturers, research centres and recyclers, and they discussed the different processes and what needs to be included in the design of the product from their own perspectives. Naturally, this led to

conflicting design requirements or missing information, which was valuable information to capture so that it can be applied in closing the loop at a later stage.

The methodology consisted in 3 phases:

1. The leader presents the product to rethink, indicating the current value chain of the product.
2. Individual work by each work group member. Each person writes down in post-its ideas corresponding to each point of the lifecycle considering different levels of recovery strategies dimensions: Energy recovery, materials recycling, and circular strategies at product level including remanufacturing, refurbishing, re-use and long use. Each person had a colour of post-it assigned so that afterwards the idea could be linked to the company.
3. Group work, where the team discuss collectively the individual contributions of phase 2, placing each idea on its appropriate category –actions & processes, challenges and design solutions-. This list of actions, challenges and potential solutions to improve the sustainability of each one of the products is, at the end, the intended outcome of the workshops and they are explained in the present deliverable.

During the workshop, a person from ITENE or TUDelft was facilitating the conversation in each group. The following questions were planned in order to guide the discussion and maintain the concentration over the topic of the workshop.

To assist the exploration of recovery options, the following questions were used:

- Material perspective:
 - What material or product is recovered here?
 - What is the quality of the material?
 - How can it be used?
 - What is needed of the material for successful (valuable) recovery?
- Stakeholder perspective:
 - Which stakeholder is the material/product delivered to?
 - What requirements would he ask for?
- Business perspective:
 - What is the value proposition of this recovery?

Questions to guide the discussion:

- What opportunities do you see for the recovery loops?
 - From the materials perspective: what qualities does the recovered material have and what can we do with it?
 - From the stakeholder perspective: what do you require from the material?
 - From a business perspective: what is the value proposition of the recovery?
- What do you think of the design framework used here?
 - Is the framework usable & clear?
 - Are the proposed design strategies relevant for your product?
- What have you found in this workshop? (can you describe in one sentence ...)
 - Which recovery loop do you think is most relevant?
 - What materials & construction issues did you find?
 - What design ideas, solutions did you think of?
 - What remains unknown?
 - What obstacles did you encounter?
 - What opportunities did you see?
- What is the next step for your product redesign process?

In Figure 1-1, Figure 1-3 and Figure 1-4 a template of the working sheet elaborated by TUDelft used in the workshop can be seen. The results of each of the working sheets are shown in Annex 1. Each of the design solutions and challenges proposed by the partners have been grouped in general solutions and challenges that manufactures of each sector can find when they try to design a product in the circular context. These results.

Product description

1 Stakeholders & lifecycles

Figure 1-4. Workshop worksheet part 1

2.5 Design solutions and main challenges

In this section the main challenges and design solutions that arouse in the workshop in order to design products in a circular manner are presented:

MAIN CHALLENGES

1. **Dis-&re-assembly complexity:** Difficulties can arise when designing a product related to dis&re-assembly methods: lack of space for screws, impossible to make the product modular, etc. These problems were pointed several times by the participants during the workshops.
2. **Customer design expectations:** Products have to be made desirable for customers, which means that a product must be designed taking into account the opinion of the final users and paying special attention to aesthetics. In this context the difficult part is to maintain the product appealing through the time (both if the final goal is to lengthen the use or if the objective is to reuse it). To make the product timeless may be a way to get it accepted for a long time. The ability to change appearance, the exterior can be a way to give product longevity. An example is mobile phones where you can change the covers. It might be an advantage of age and wear that gives the product "patina" as extra value.
3. **Mechanical requirements:** When materials, the surface treatment or structural design change, it is easy that the product faces mechanical problems. Take into account all mechanical and safety requirements before deciding which design solutions are going to be applied.
4. **Modularity complexity:** Difficulties can arise when designing a product to be modular: lack of space for screws, impossible to separate pieces, etc. These problems were pointed several times by the participants during the workshops.
5. **Mechanical recycling challenges:** Compatibility of coatings with recycling processes.
6. **Nonexistence market:** There is a lack of recycled materials in the EU market. This jeopardises the capability of doing recycled products or components. This is mainly because of the lower amount of this type of products or because it is not cost-effective either.
7. **Material contamination:** Due to the production or the recovery processes, materials can get contaminated through many of the steps involved. Thus, assuring that recycled, reused or remanufactured materials are free of contaminants is such a challenge.

8. **Sorting challenges.** The majority of black plastic is coloured using carbon black pigments which do not enable the product to be sorted by the optical sorting systems being used widely in plastics recycling (NIR technology). As a result, black plastics commonly end up as residue and is disposed of in landfill or recycled into lower value materials where polymer sorting is not required.
9. **Economics:** Recycling will ultimately lead to resource and energy saving. Various technologies, mostly focusing on reinforcement fibres and yet to be commercialized, have been developed: mechanical recycling, thermal recycling, and chemical recycling. However, lack of adequate markets, high recycling cost, and lower quality of the recyclates are the major commercialization barriers. To promote composites recycling, extensive R&D efforts are still needed on development of ground-breaking better recyclable composites and much more efficient separation technologies (Yang, 2012).
10. **Durability challenges:** Whilst the life expectancy of products has traditionally been predicted from previous in-service experience, the use of materials in more demanding applications requires a far better understanding of the failure mechanisms that determine a component's life expectancy.
11. **Regulation limitations:** products cannot be produced the way manufacturers want. They need to follow the legislation, specially the hazardous substances contents allowance.
12. **Traceability control:** Products should be identified along the whole value chain. Traceability information is important in order to check the origin of the products/materials, that they do not contain hazardous substances, and to know where exactly they have been along the process.
13. **Adaptability issues:** The key feature of a product is that it in an optimal way fulfils the customer's needs. Try to meet the customer's real needs. There are different business models that can be interesting in the case of remanufacturing. You can sell a remanufactured product to your customer, but you might also rent it to him or maybe just sell the function and provide him with the necessary equipment. Your product needs to adapt to the customer's requirements.
14. **Collection challenges:** It is not easy to collect bulky waste for the manufacturers. Once the manufacturers do not own the product anymore, it is not possible to assure entirely that they will get it back once its lifecycle has end to apply any of the recovery strategies.
15. **People' lack of awareness:** the general public attitude must change towards a more sustainable consumption habit. In this sense, it is always preferred to reuse

products instead of buying new ones, and if it is essential to buy another product, check the remanufactured options (always with their quality assurance) before the totally new ones.

DESIGN SOLUTIONS

1. **Dis-&re-assembly:** Active Disassembly use design practices that incorporate smart materials and processes to enable the rapid and non-destructive disassembly of products and components. Active Disassembly address some of the barriers associated with designing for remanufacture, including cost of new design, time, labour and quality of recovered components. Make the product easy to demount. Screws, snaps, clips are normally preferred. Welding, rivets, folding, gluing, etc. can make a joint more difficult to demount. Use the same type, and size, of joining elements (screws) to make it possible to use only one tool during demounting. Make the joining points easy to access if possible from one side and aligned in one direction¹⁰

Tips for manufacturers for easy dis&re-assembly:

- Note which parts of a product may need to be disassembled at a reuse. Make these parts easy to disassemble.
- Make sure that you can easily access all of the items to be disassembled and that this can be done with the appropriate tool. It shall also be possible to simultaneously view the points.
- It is good if all points to be dismantled can be reached from a single direction.
- The product should have adequate fastening points so that you can manage it by a remanufacturing either on a working bench or in any equipment needed for the process.
- Sometimes it might be appropriate to leave room for new screw holes that will be needed by the remanufacturing.
- Reversible fasteners, that can be reused, is usually good.
- Show where fasteners are seated in order to facilitate the dismantling. Do not hide them. View if needed with an instruction type arrow.
- Screws are normally good for disassembly.

¹⁰ Ellen MacArthur Foundation. Web: <https://www.ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/case-studies/techniques-for-rapid-non-destructive-disassembly>

- Use one type and a size so that you can use one single tool.
 - Make sure that you can access the screw with a tool, for example, a screwdriver. If there is a nut you must also have access to the back side.
 - If possible use screws of type Torx and Insex that does not provide the lifting forces at loss and tightening
 - Screws of type pozi-drive are also relatively good.
 - Snap fasteners are good for disassembly.
 - There are normal snap fasteners that are integrated into the details usually of plastics.
 - There are snap fasteners that are pressed into place.
 - Sometimes a Velcro can be a suitable fastener.
 - Clips are good for disassembly.
 - Adhesives - are generally not preferred if the product must be dismantled at a remanufacturing.
 - If the adhesive is to be used is the best alternative water-based adhesives.
 - Breakpoints can be good for glued joints which must be broken.
 - Rivets - are not preferred for disassembly.
 - Welding - is not preferred for disassembly.
 - To join parts by folding - is not preferred for disassembly.
 - Staples (for staple gun) - are difficult to remove.
2. **Modularity:** Enforcing "conformance of assembly configurations to dimensional standards based on modular 'building block' units of standardized size, shape, and interface locations (e.g., locations for mating attachment or mounting points and input/output line connectors), in order to simplify maintenance tasks by enabling the use of standardized assembly/ disassembly procedures" (Moss, 1985).
 3. **Identification:** Provide the product with an identification. This can be done with a tag, barcode, QR code, or even with a simple text placed on the product. Mark if possible different parts with the type of material. For plastics use existing systems. This will help in the traceability, making easy the recovery of products.
 4. **Interchangeability:** "Controlling dimensional and functional tolerances of manufactured parts and assemblies to assure that [a part that is expected to fail or has failed] soon can be replaced in the field with no physical rework required

for achieving a physical fit, and with a minimum of adjustments needed for achieving proper functioning” (Moss, 1985)

5. **Material Selection:** Use materials, parts and components that will be available in the future. Keep in mind the second use of a remanufactured product. Use materials that do not degenerate during the multiple use faces. Pay attention to chemicals and additives that can be present in materials. Avoid those that now or later are harmful and might be banned. Avoid those that can cause problems during the remanufacturing process. REACH is a regulation with a list of banned materials and a list of materials to be banned. Consider multiple lifecycles. Use materials which are strong enough. Avoid materials that might lose strength, become brittle or get discoloured. Do not incorporate any chemicals that might be banned later on.
6. **Surface treatment selection:** Selecting the type of surface treatment (for example anodizing, painting, plating or coating (Bijen (2003)) best suited to the design requirements of the product under consideration.

The surface of a product is the visible part, hence, if it is damaged the customer will think of changing the product for a new one. Coatings which help to avoid scratching will improve the appearance of a product, making its life longer. Select the surface treatment that is resistant to the desired number of lifecycles. Select surface treatment which can be removed if it must be renewed. No toxins should be present. Make sure that in case of being recycled this coating won't affect negatively the recycling process.

7. **Sorting:** Each product needs to be sorted. This could happen by density, with a magnetic or electric field, or by using other physical or mechanical characteristics of the material we want to separate. The chosen mechanism depends on the material mix. Ferrous materials are easy to separate from aluminium by using a magnetic field. But if we are trying to separate aluminium from a mix of polymers, then a magnetic field is not the right mechanism to choose.

Be aware of how the sorting process of the product works to make a good selection of materials and shapes so that the it can be sorted efficiently.

8. **Malfunction annunciation:** Add a structural way to obtain a diagnostic of the old, worn out product. This assists you to clarify what has to be done to the product to give it a second life.
9. **Structural design:** Try to gather all parts that need to be updated in one subassembly. Avoid cross-dependencies that makes it necessary to update one

module as a consequence of updating in another one. Make a "kit" with all the elements required for an update.

10. **Fastener and connection selection:** The product should have adequate fastening points so that you can manage it by a remanufacturing either on a working bench or in any equipment needed for the process. Sometimes it might be appropriate to leave room for new screw holes that will be needed by the remanufacturing.

*See "Tips for manufacturers for easy dis&re-assembly"

11. **Documentation:** Save data about the product on the web or in any other suitable way. Appropriate data can be content of materials and procedure for the remanufacturing, but it can also be any other data regarding the product. There must be product information, also a link where the data about the product could be found. Give information about how to make the product last longer and how to dispose it to give a second life to the product.

12. **Planning:** Start the designing phase by thinking in all stages of the products life and all lifecycles available. Take into account all possible design solutions during the design process. An initial LCA can give very useful information for decision-makers in order to decide which of the alternatives can be more appropriate to close the loop of the product.

13. **Simplify:** Try to reduce to the minimum the number of pieces and parts of each product. Avoid using chemicals and dangerous substances.

14. **Adaptability:** Allowing a product to be continually updated (Keoleian, 1993) or to "perform several different functions" (Keoleian, 1993).

Updating allows a product to keep performing the functions it was originally designed for in a changing environment whereas upgrading enhances the functionality of a product.

15. **New business models:** Although this is not directly a design solution, there is a need to establish a solid market around circular economy. Products should be part of an integrated business model focusing on the delivery of a performance or functional service. Competition should be mainly based on the creation of added service value of a product, not solely on its sales value. Social/business model innovation allows the creation of extra value by applying technological innovation to solving societal needs. As products are part of a company's assets, cost minimisation drives product longevity, reuse, reparability and remanufacturing.

16. **Standardisation:** Enforcing "the conformance of commonly used parts and assemblies ... to generally accepted design standards for configuration,

dimensional tolerances, performance ratings and other functional design attributes" (Moss, 1985)

17. **EU regulation:** Although this is not directly a design solution, there is a need of updating the regulation across Europe.

3 Composite recovery in the automotive industry (Input from Irina Ferreres (BELLVER-INCOTEC))

3.1 Recovery perspective

3.1.1 Design

Nowadays, the design of the vehicles does not help plastic parts recovery at all. This is because the vehicles arrive in very bad conditions or compressed to recycling and recovery process. Moreover, they are mechanically crushed to make the separation of the components easier. If a priori separation of the fragmentation process is to be proposed, the market value of recovered material should be higher than the cost of its extraction.

The main points to separate a part are: easy identification, size and profitability of the operation, which combines ease of extraction, and high possibility of reusing for the same purpose or another of enough economic value. Legislation also boost these actions, as it is the case of fuels, oils and lead batteries, which are compulsorily extracted.

In scrapping it should be possible to locate and separate the most important parts to recover, before or after the first pressing. This should be easy should in terms of material, size or colour and low manpower.

3.1.2 Present situation

Currently, recovered plastics are the easiest to identify, such as the fuel tank ABS, but little or nothing else, since they are all crushed and mixed in 150X100 millimetres granulometries.

The batteries are removed in the scrap-yard together with the fuel and the oils. The tires are easily identifiable and removable. The fuel tank that is already empty is notable for its volume and the thickness of the walls. Even after the first pressing it can be extracted with relative ease and economic profitability.

3.1.3 Tools & machines

The machines that are used (in a very schematized way) are:

1. Fragmenter that separates iron fractions from plastics and other metals

2. Metal Plant Section: Separation process by currents of Foucault, to separate the aluminium; and detectors "Finder" from Tomra, to separate the copper from the plastics.

To be able to optimize the process we would need to organize several times the same equipment in series on the same flow, to increase the efficiency of the process in a cycle.

3.1.4 Changes in type of materials

At the moment, the changes in type of materials affect the recovery companies in a negative way, due to the lack of skill to classify and revalue plastics, while decreasing the metal content in the vehicle. This causes the value of recovery of the vehicles out of use (EoL vehicles) to decrease (sales figure); and increase the amount of material that goes to landfill or incineration, with greater expense for us and environmental impact for everybody.

The needs of our sector could be addressed by unifying the plastics and composites or developing more effective methods of classification and recovery of these for re-entry into the industrial cycle again.

3.1.5 Other comments

The best option, under recovery companies' criteria, in order to increase the value of actual waste and reduce environmental impact by reducing the material going to landfill, would be **to find processes and machines that can effectively and efficiently separate each different plastic**. This would allow starting valuing current and future out-of-use vehicles that are already in the market. In other cases, such as just unify criteria for plastic production of future cars; we could start to recover and value plastics within 25- or 30-years' time.

3.2 Main challenges

The main challenges which the automotive sector may face when designing for a circular economy are related with the customers perspective about a remanufactured or reused product. Obviously in the automotive sector the appearance of a product is extremely important, hence is a matter of change people's mindset in order to make them understand that a reused or remanufactured product is not worse than a new one.

On the other hand, the challenge which has also been extremely mentioned is "mechanical requirements". This points out if a reused or remanufactured product will have exactly the same mechanical requirements as a new one.

Next, Table 3, presents a summary of the most important challenges for the participants of the workshop. For further information, consult Annex I.

Table 3. Summary of the most important challenges of the Automotive working group

Main Challenges Automotive	Materials	Products			
	Recycling	Remanufacturing	Refurbishing	Re-use	Long use
Dis-&re-assembly complexity	X	X			
Customer design expectations		X	X	X	X
Mechanical requirements	X	X	X		X
Modularity complexity			X		X
Mechanical recycling challenges	X				
Nonexistence market					
Material contamination	X				
Sorting challenges	X				
Economics	X				
Durability challenges			X		X
Environmental challenges	X				
Regulation limitations					
Traceability control					
Adaptability issues					
Collection challenges					
People lack of awareness	X				

According to the questionnaire sent after the workshop, the main challenges found by the people who answered the questionnaire for the automotive sector were:

- *“The low material value in market” (FASCIA CONSOLE)*
- *“Identifying the kind of material.” (FASCIA CONSOLE)*
- *“Disassemble costs” (FASCIA CONSOLE)*
- *“material properties” (FASCIA CONSOLE)*
- *“Economic and Technical viability of the thermoplastic compounds extruded from recycled materials at the EoL step of the cars.” (FASCIA CONSOLE)*
- *“the use of mixed materials that can’t easily be separated” (CENTRAL CONSOLE COWLINGS)*
- *“The challenge I found intriguing was the fact that once a car has reached its end-of-life, the components which can be easily removed (and are indeed designed for easy disassembly for repair) are not separated but rather, the whole car crushed down. This means that in terms of component design and material, there is no problem. The problem lies on the fact that even though components and materials can be re-used, they are not because there is a gap which needs to be filled in the product life chain (in this case, a place where components are disassembled, and materials re-used)” (SAFETY BELT BRACKETS)*

3.3 Design solutions

When designing a product, several aspects must be taken into account. During the workshop, the most commented solution was the material selection. The right material should be sought in order to fulfil the product requirements in the short, but also in the long term. Besides, in order to be able to reuse it afterwards, the participants highlighted the simplification. The simpler the product, the more reusability.

Table 4 shows, as it can be seen, the most preferred design solutions in the automotive sector. To consult all the detailed results, the reader should go to Annex I.

Table 4. Summary of the preferred design solutions for the Automotive working group

Design solutions Automotive	Materials	Products			
	Recycling	Remanufacturing	Refurbishing	Re-use	Long use
Dis-&re-assembly				X	X
Modularity	X			X	
Identification					X
Interchangeability					
Material selection	X	X	X	X	
surface treatment selection			X	X	
Sorting	X				
Malfunction annunciation					
Structural design	X	X		X	
Fastener & connection selection			X		
Documentation					
Planning				X	
Simplify	X	X		X	
Adaptability				X	
New business model				X	
Standardisation				X	
EU Regulations				X	

According to the questionnaire sent after the workshop, the main challenges found by the people who answered the questionnaire for the automotive sector were:

- *"Recycling." (FASCIA CONSOLE)*
- *"Automatization of plastics' identification when shredded" (FASCIA CONSOLE)*
- *"less weight, simple but stable structure" (FASCIA CONSOLE)*
- *"2K injected multifunctional parts made of recycled thermoplastic compounds." (FASCIA CONSOLE)*
- *"increased modular design and non-permanent fixing and bonding methods" (CENTRAL CONSOLE COWLINGS)*
- *"Building incentives (perhaps economical) for institutions/companies and/or end-users to disassemble components at the end-of life of cars." (SAFETY BELT BRACKETS)*

Figure 3-1. The most important design solutions for the automotive sector according to the questionnaire results

3.4 Recovery strategies

For the automotive sector, as can be seen in Table 3, the recovery strategy which includes more challenges which may difficult the design for circularity is Recycling. This can be due to the difficulties that the recycling process may entail with different material qualities, such as composites.

On the other hand, the recovery strategy with more design solutions found was Reuse, which makes it the easiest one to implement, paying special attention on what consumers will think about reusing a product, and trying to make it attractive for them.

Figure 3-2. The most important recovery strategies for the automotive sector according to the questionnaire average results

4 Composite recovery in the furniture industry (based on input from Giovanni Tosi (MORETTI))

4.1 Recovery perspective

4.1.1 Design

According to studies, the amount of post-consumer wood generated in the EU 27 in 2007 was estimated by Mantau et al. to be 55.4 Mm³. These researchers stated that these volumes were disposed of by land-filling (37%), burning with energy recovery (30%) and

Figure 4-1. The most important recovery strategies for the automotive sector according to the product owners (questionnaire results)

particleboard manufacture (30%). However, the main end-uses for recovered wood are: wood-based panel manufacture; biomass energy generation; animal bedding;

mulches; equine surfaces; pathways and coverings. All of these use wood in the form of particles. None of these end-uses, except panel manufacture, permit a second life-cycle and so the stored carbon is released.

4.1.2 Present situation

Recovery and recycling wood at a larger commercial scale is still a relatively recent phenomenon across Europe and some countries like Germany, Italy and Great Britain are more advanced than others. Nevertheless, all countries are striving to setup the legislative framework and infra-structure necessary to ensure that the majority of wood is recycled in some way: in this sense, there is still a lot to be developed under the technical point of view with the aim to give all necessary instruments to be exploited for the implementation, at European level, of an integrated and functional wood recycling system.

4.1.3 Tools & machines

Considering its nature, waste wood is very heterogeneous: in fact, it's very common the utilization of a wide range of products that are made up with various wood species and non-wood components like paints, adhesives, metal fixings and plastics with different mechanical, physical and chemical properties. At the moment, there are solution for mechanical treatment, sorting and reprocessing systems to ensure mainly that non-contaminated wood is recycled into new products. In this context, it will be necessary the implementation of innovative technological solutions for the chemical and mechanical contaminants sorting and removal such as:

- technologies for metal and non-wooden materials recovery from complex products
- technologies (detection and removing systems) to improve the cleanliness of recovered wood, by enhancing the purity of wood from chemical contaminants such as preservatives
- technologies to process and dispose contaminated removed parts
- technology for wood product components sorted by quality
- technology for the introduction of the recycled component in new products

In parallel, another activity will be the realization of a multi-criteria analysis in order to assess all the economic, social and environmental aspects of the whole recycling chain

4.1.4 Changes in type of materials and development of non-toxic binder solutions

At European level, the priority is the optimization of the collection and aggregation processes of scraps, in order to have quantities of recycled wood sufficiently large to guarantee the economic viability: thus, it is necessary the development of an organized technical and logistic mechanism ensuring the recycling of the majority of wood as well as the minimization of losses; this activity will be the necessary prerequisite to adopt legislative and infrastructural measures by policy makers and stakeholders in general. Part of the work will be also addressed for the development of new methodologies related to the product design, with the aim to increase the recyclability of the products and all their components.

It's important to highlight that wood (especially for furniture production) can be, more than substituted, combined with other recycled or natural materials in order to obtain new products with eco-sustainability features. Consequently, it will also be possible to develop new markets and increase the competitiveness of European production related to the wood recycling process.

4.1.5 Other comments

One of the most significant impact is a better collecting process that will increase the quantity of recycled wood and, at the same time, that will reduce losses. The research activity will be an important instrument for stakeholders and policy makers in order to effectively implement an enhanced collecting and sorting system. On the other hand, about quality, the development of technologies will contribute to the realization of high values products like nano-crystalline cellulose, xylose and lignin-based adhesives: in this regard, it will be also important the contribution of the legislative framework through the reduction of the regulatory limits.

The enhancement of recycling process under the qualitative and quantitative point of view will be useful to further encourage the utilization of recycled wood for the manufacture of high-value products: at the moment in fact, wood wastes are recycled in the form of particles and the majority of recovered wood is used to make particleboard products (e.g. furniture components); moreover, the next most widespread method is to burn the recovered wood with energy recovery. Other end-uses include animal beddings and landscape mulches, but in general, the use of recovered wood in particle form has a very little added value. In this sense, the development of alternative recycling methods will **add much more value to the recovered wood** and this would provide more money for the recycling processes and, in turn, encourage more recycling.

4.2 Main challenges

Manufacturers face lots of challenges during the production of their products, and more if the product is designed for the circularity. In the case of the workshop carried out in Koblenz, the participants evaluated as biggest challenges for the furniture sector, for instance, the dis-/re-assembly complexity or the mechanical requirements of the products.

Table 5 shows the summary of the most important challenges identified along the workshop by the furniture sector. All results can be consulted in Annex I.

Table 5. Summary of the most important challenges of the Furniture working group

Main Challenges Furniture	Materials	Products			
	Recycling	Remanufacturing	Refurbishing	Re-use	Long use
Dis-&re-assembly complexity			X	X	X
Customer design expectations				X	X
Mechanical requirements	X	X			X
Modularity complexity		X		X	
Mechanical recycling challenges	X				
Nonexistence market	X				
Material contamination	X				X
Sorting challenges	X				
Economics					
Durability challenges			X		X
Environmental challenges		X			X
Regulation limitations					
Traceability control			X		X
Adaptability issues				X	
Collection challenges	X				X
People lack of awareness				X	

According to the questionnaire sent after the workshop, the main challenges found by the people who answered the questionnaire for the furniture sector were:

- *“Quality of materials” (BOOKCASE)*
- *“Changing panel colour” (BOOKCASE)*
- *“The uncertainty of the bio-based binder solution” (BOOKCASE)*

4.3 Design solutions

Table 6 summarises the design solutions that the participants of the workshop selected as preferred. All the detailed information can be found in Annex I. During the workshop we did not get to the point of discussing design solutions. We raised issues and concerns to be considered but not come up with strategies to address them.

Table 6. Summary of the preferred design solutions for the Furniture working group

Design solutions Furniture	Materials	Products			
	Recycling	Remanufacturing	Refurbishing	Re-use	Long use
Dis-&re-assembly			X	X	
Modularity		X	X		
Identification					
Interchangeability			X		
Material selection	X				X
surface treatment selection	X				X
Sorting					
Malfunction annunciation					
Structural design					X
Fastener & connection selection		X	X	X	
Documentation				X	X
Planning			X	X	X
Simplify		X			
Adaptability			X		X
New business model	X			X	X
Standardisation				X	
EU Regulations	X			X	

According to the questionnaire sent after the workshop, the main challenges found by the people who answered the questionnaire for the furniture sector were:

- "Modularity" (BOOKCASE)
- "Cubic design" (BOOKCASE)
- "Local raw material possibilities of binder synthesis" (BOOKCASE)

Figure 4-2. The most important design solutions for the furniture sector according to the questionnaire results

4.4 Recovery strategies

For the furniture sector, as can be seen in Table 5, the recovery strategy which includes more challenges which may difficult the design for circularity is Long use. This can be due to the difficulties of the material to maintain the same properties along time. Durability challenges or material contamination were two of the main challenges selected by the participants. Besides, recycling can be problematic too, due to the mechanical recycling processes and the sorting and collection challenges.

On the other hand, and regarding the recovery strategy where more design solutions appeared, Table 6 shows that there is a tie between Reuse and Long use. The common design solutions appointed for both strategies are, for example, documentation, planning or the implementation of new business models within the new circular economy transition.

Figure 4-4. The most important design solutions for the furniture according to the questionnaire average results

Figure 4-3. The most important design solutions for the furniture according to the product owner (questionnaire results)

5 Composite recovery in the building industry (Input from Markku Vilkki (CONENOR))

5.1 Recovery perspective

5.1.1 Design

Buildings and constructions are more and more complex from 1980 onwards in terms of type of materials (polymeric foams, composites, thermal insulation materials), execution techniques of such materials (materials adhered to each other, spray materials, sandwich systems like plasterboards) or hazardous potential of specific materials (polyurethane insulating foams containing hydrofluorcarbons or other ozone depleting substances). Over the first decades of the current XXI century, ever more complex systems (e.g. solar panels and other renewable energy systems for buildings) and nanotechnology based multifunctional materials (e.g. phase change materials, ultralight materials, self-cleaning materials, self-healing materials) are emerging but their market uptake is still negligible and consequently will not constitute a massive problem in Construction & Demolition Waste (C&DW) till 2050 onwards. An efficient recovery of raw materials from ever more complex buildings requires both an enhanced segregation of materials at the source and new integral recycling approaches aiming to capture a higher value of those resources embodied in the subsequent C&DW flows (Pielke, 1981).

5.1.2 Present situation

Construction and demolition waste (CDW) are one of the most significant waste streams in the EU representing 25 - 30 % share of all waste generation in the EU11. Recent studies concluded that EU28 countries generated approximately 460 Mt of CDW (excluding excavation materials) in 2005 and the generation rates are expected to reach 516 Mt in 2020 and around 570 Mt between 2025 and 2030¹². The share of wood-based materials was estimated to be 2 to 4 % from total CDW amount¹². However, in the Nordic countries the proportion of CDW wood could be a very high, reaching the 40 % level¹². The recycling rate of CDW wood is low and approximately 70 % of the material is currently being disposed at landfills or used in energy recovery purposes¹². The largest recycling usage of CDW wood is to use material as a raw material in the production of particle and fiber boards, but CDW wood is also used for example in ground covers and animal beddings¹². At present, wood waste is mainly incinerated with energy recovery,

¹¹ European Commission. Web: http://ec.europa.eu/environment/waste/construction_demolition.htm

¹² European Commission DG ENV (2011) "Management of Construction and demolition waste in EU", Final Report elaborated by BIO Intelligence Service.

The global construction industry is showing substantial growth which has been driving demand for cement and concrete (Table 7). One of the key drivers behind the growth is urbanization particularly in emerging markets. Meanwhile, rising per capita income is also underpinning demand for cement and concrete in the residential construction sector. Growth in urban population is a major megatrend, which is transforming the construction industry in most countries. Among the most important market players, both in terms of concrete production and cement consumption, Turkey, USA and Japan can be found. Several European countries, such as Germany, France and UK, also belong to the group of key players, but their role is not so significant.

Table 7. Demand of cement and concrete of the construction sector

Country	Concrete production ¹ millions of m ³			Cement consumption ¹ millions of tons			Gross Domestic Product ² billions of €		
	2014	2015	2016	2014	2015	2016	2014	2015	2016
AT-Austria	14.3	15.0	15.0	5.1	5.1	4.7	307.5	310.5	315.1
BE-Belgium	21.4	21.4	22.0	6.1	6.4	6.5	378.1	383.6	388.2
CZ-Czech Republic	10.0	10.0	10.0	3.4	2.6	2.8	161.7	169.1	173.2
DK-Denmark	4.3	4.4	4.4	1.4	1.5	1.6	253.5	257.5	260.8
FI-Finland	3.9	3.8	4.4	1.7	1.6	1.9	186.6	187.1	189.6
FR-France	51.0	48.0	49.5	18.1	17.2	17.7	2075.0	2097.2	2122.1
DE-Germany	77.4	77.4	77.4	27.1	26.6	26.6	2743.9	2791.1	2843.2
IE-Ireland	2.8	2.8	2.8	1.2	1.4	1.6	181.2	228.8	240.7
IT-Italy	40.0	35.0	32.0	21.6	19.6	18.6	1542.9	1555.0	1568.7
NL-Netherlands	11.6	13.0	13.0	4.1	4.0	4.2	643.0	655.6	670.0
PL-Poland	33.7	34.0	35.2	15.4	15.9	15.8	404.3	419.8	431.1
PT-Portugal	5.5	5.5	5.5	2.6	2.4	2.5	169.1	171.8	174.2
SK-Slovakia	2.1	2.5	2.5	1.8	1.7	1.7	73.5	76.3	78.9
ES-Spain	31.0	32.5	32.5	10.8	11.4	11.3	1035.1	1068.3	1102.9
SE-Sweden	-	-	-	2.2	2.3	2.8	392.5	408.5	421.5
UK-United Kingdom	37.0	39.0	39.0	10.9	9.4	9.4	1980.1	2023.6	2060.1
Total/Average EU	346.0	344.3	345.2	133.5	129.0	129.6	12528	12804	13040
IL-Israel	14.5	17.1	17.0	6.0	6.5	6.5	0.0	0.0	0.0
NO-Norway	5.0	5.0	5.5	2.0	1.9	2.1	0.0	0.0	0.0
CH-Switzerland	-	-	-	4.6	4.6	4.2	469.0	472.9	472.9
TR-Turkey	121.0	123.0	129.0	63.0	63.7	66.8	771.9	818.6	818.6
Total/Average ERMCO	486.5	489.4	496.7	209.1	205.7	209.2	13769	14095	14332
RU-Russia	72.0	62.0	58.0	68.5	62.1	61.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
USA-United States	330.0	365.0	370.0	82.0	92.0	94.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
JP-Japan	138.0	138.0	138.0	47.0	47.0	47.0	0.0	0.0	0.0

Bricks are a widely used construction and building material around the world. Clay type, sand lime, and fly ash clay are the most common type of bricks used in the construction sector. Conventional bricks are produced from clay with high temperature kiln firing or from ordinary Portland cement (OPC) concrete, and thus contain high embodied energy and have large carbon footprint. In many areas of the world, there is already a shortage of natural source material for production of the conventional bricks. For environmental protection and sustainable development, extensive research has been conducted on production of bricks from waste materials.

The global concrete block and brick manufacturing market is gaining from the booming construction sector worldwide. the global concrete block and brick manufacturing market to expand at a moderate 3.8% compound annual growth rate (CAGR) for the forecast period 2017-2027. At this pace, the market evaluated at 1,837.48 billion units in 2016 will

become 2769.24 billion units by 2027 end. It is worth noting, however, that contrary to the global trend, European market loses its potential, at least in terms of production of bricks. Eurostat reports the production value of the EU's bricks and roof tiles industry which, between 2007 and 2012, decreased from a level of 8.7 billion euros to roughly of 5.5 billion euros (i.e. -36%).

The Waste Directive 2008/98/EC, states that reuse, recycling and other material recovery of non-hazardous CDW should be increased to 70 % level in the EU by 2020. On the other hand, the Landfill Directive 1999/31/EC requires that EU countries should reduce landfilling of municipal biodegradable waste (including also wood waste from construction) to 35 % level from the level existed in year 1995 by 2016. Tightening regulations together with environmental benefits achieved by CDW recycling will rise the need to increase the recycling rate of CDW significantly in the future.

5.1.3 Tools & machines

Selective demolition and refurbishment emerge as the key to decrease the complexity of waste flows from buildings, thereby reducing flows to landfill and creating high-value raw material streams for recycling. The main problems of selective demolition are cost and lack of common procedures at European level boosting and facilitating the benchmarking within the demolition sector: how to do it efficiently, making maximum use of the raw material value to get a return on the investment. It can be said that there is already a large body of experience and technologies with good dismantling. However, it is scattered over some individuals and companies. In addition, there is still a lack of standardized procedures for identification and quantification of materials arising from complex buildings, even in its most basic form. Some countries do not evidence history of selective sorting practices at source (Finlayson-Pitts, 1986).

Selective demolition and refurbishment must be combined with advanced recycling technologies to achieve high-value secondary resources from C&DW. Since the current stock of buildings was not designed for an ideal deconstruction/dismantling of components, the selective demolition, per se, does not guarantee the highest value of the recovered materials. Materials stuck to each other or composites are very common in existing buildings. Also, mixed stony fractions composed of concrete and masonry are likely to arise, even when selective demolition procedures are considered (Tennekes, 1982).

Wood waste from construction and demolition activities may be divided into waste during the construction, refurbishment and demolition activities. Wood waste from the construction site may be handled so that contamination and weather exposure is avoided. In the Nordic countries, wood is traditionally used in casting of foundations of

constructions and infra works, e.g. bridges. Pure wood fraction during the construction phase may be sorted out using a rather simple sorting process for potential use. However, the wood waste from casting, contains concrete residues which might hamper recycling. The recycled wood from a demolition site will probably be contaminated in different ways and to a greater extent and needs more processing before use compared to waste from the construction. Typical wood materials from refurbishment are interior materials (e.g. walls, beams, furniture).

When aiming to achieve higher incorporation levels of C&DW recycled materials (recycled aggregates, ceramic particles, gypsum or wood) into new building materials or products following circular economy principles, more accurate and real-time quality control systems are required. The lack of efficient inline inspection techniques to determine quality (e.g. pollutants, hazardous substances) of the bulkstreams of recovered materials from C&DW is a major worry. It is difficult to prove the quality without the target assessment and recordable data from inline sensors. Consequently, many high-grade building applications (diverse types of concrete, bricks, composites, plasterboards) that might metabolize higher amounts of C&DW recycled materials restrict the maximum incorporation of such secondary raw materials.

The use of optic and laser-based techniques has recently revealed high potential for both accurate characterisations of raw materials recycled from C&DW and chemical analysis of particles. On the basis of such promising results from recent research works, this action line is becoming a topic of wider academic-industrial interest. One of the most interesting tools is BIM.

BIM Applications in the Project Life Cycle

BIM applications spans over the entire life cycle of a facility. This section presents a brief overview of important BIM applications in the project programming, design, preconstruction, construction, and post-construction (operations and maintenance) phases.

BIM in the Preconstruction Phase

The applications of BIM in the preconstruction phase can be summarized as follows:

- Estimating: From building information models, the contractors can perform fairly accurate quantity survey and prepare detailed estimates. Based on the data of 32 major projects, the Stanford University's Center for Integrated Facilities Engineering (CIFE) reported that the accuracy of BIM-based estimates was within 3% with up to 80%-time reduction in generating these estimates (cited by CRC Construction Innovation, 2007).

- Site coordination: Using 3D or 4D site coordination models, the contractors can plan for site logistics, develop traffic layouts, and identify potential hazards at the jobsite which can aid in preparing a more realistic site safety plan.
- Constructability analysis: Using BIM models, the project team can perform detailed constructability analysis to plan sequence of operations at the jobsite.

BIM in the Construction Phase

In the construction phase, the project team can use BIM for the following activities: (1) Project progress monitoring using 4D phasing plans; (2) For trade coordination meetings (see Figure 5); and (3) Integrating RFIs, change orders and punch list information in the BIM models. Throughout the construction period, the project team must continuously update the BIM model so that it reflects the most up-to-date information which later on can be used by the facility managers for building operations and maintenance.

BIM in the Post construction Phase

A building information model contains complete information about a facility as it evolves through planning, design and construction. This information can be leveraged for downstream use by facility managers thereby making operations and maintenance of a facility more efficient. Research suggests that 85% of the lifecycle cost of a facility occurs after construction is completed and approximately \$10 billion are annually lost in the U.S. alone due to inadequate information access and interoperability issues during operations and maintenance phases (Newton, 2004). The use of BIM for facility management (FM) can significantly help to prevent these losses.

The fundamental benefit of a BIM model is that it provides information about a building and its spaces, systems and components. The overall goal is to transfer these data into facility management operations. In this manner information about building systems and equipment can be accessed by simply clicking on an object in a BIM model. For example, the information that is extracted for a piece of equipment such as a VAV box are location, name, model number, product type, operation and maintenance manuals, commissioning information and performance data. This makes it very simple for a maintenance worker to access the required information vital to different systems in the building as shown in Figure 6 (Philips and Azhar, 2011).

In what kind of situations BIM is used?

Taking into account different types of buildings, it should be noted that the BIM solutions are the most popular among companies aimed at construction of commercial buildings (offices, retail or hotels) and, followed by institutional or other public constructions. The

group of the most important advantages of the BIM solutions includes the following aspects:

- Routinely using BIM's 3D visualization capabilities to communicate with all parties.
- Using BIM on the job site to guide construction activities.
- Increasing time spent on design.
- BIM reviews in collaboration environments with multiple parties.

The first factor is seen as the most important in all surveyed groups: architects, engineers, contractors and owners. As a result, the 3D visualization capabilities may play a key role in the process of commercialization of different BIM solutions.

5.1.4 Changes in type of materials

In recent past ten years wood-plastic composites (WPC) have started gaining rapidly popularity among house owners and builders. Key benefits of WPCs vs. wood is that it does not absorb moisture and thus will not swell, rot nor splinter. It keeps its original properties over years and does not require maintenance not painting because the product is not painted at all, but pigments are integral part of the material formulation giving the desired aesthetics during production on-line. Main applications are decking, fencing and siding in private consumer market but also one may find the product in outdoor sports arenas, cafes and pathways in commercial use, too. Outside of Europe in areas like Asia and South-America WPC have become used also in more volume structural applications in constructing small buildings, storages and equal, however not yet in Europe. In North-America vinyl siding made from PVC for homes and industrial buildings has become popular and is well established in the market. It does exist also in European markets but is less popular.

The global wood plastic composites market was valued at USD 4.37 billion in 2016 and is expected to reach USD 8.76 billion in 2022, growing at a CAGR of 12.3%. In terms of volume, global wood plastic composites stood at approximately 4,262.3 kilotons in 2016. The global wood plastic composites (WPC) market is expected to reach USD 5,991.2 million by 2021, growing at a CAGR of more than 11%. WPCs are relative news and yet unknown products in the European market, but volumes are growing rapidly. Total production in 2016 is estimated to be around 250.000 tons and the number of manufacturers around 60 including both compounded material suppliers and product manufacturers. Main countries for sales are Germany, France and Benelux.

While polymers used in the European WPCs are the three main bulk polymers i.e. either PE, PVC or PP, natural fibres may come from various sources and their origin is versatile. Some manufacturers purchase ready-made wood fibres from their suppliers e.g.

Rettenmaier & Sohn in Germany but most have their own sources where-ever. One WPC-manufacturer category is the ones who get natural fibre supplies from their sister companies' production side streams and waste. This applies especially well for Finland with the sole two current WPC-manufacturers UPM ProFi <http://www.upmprofi.com/Pages/default.aspx> and Lunacomp <http://lunacomp.fi/eng/> . UPM Group ProFi is using its sister company Raflatac paper waste which is an industrial side stream from label feed stock production. (note; development of UPM ProFi was originally initiated 2004 and managed by Conenor Ltd in Finland). Lunacomp is utilizing its parent company Lunawood thermowood shavings and residues which is of local pine wood origin.

C&DW wood is currently not being used in notable volumes WPC-manufacturing in Europe. This is likely not seen an attractive choice while other sources for clean wood fibres are yet found relatively easy for the current market volumes and limited demand. WPCs are sold at high premium prices vs. wood (pressure treated) and thus manufacturers are not yet searching for lowest possible cost alternatives for wood fibre supplies – which would involve themselves is quality, homogeneity and incoming inspection issues much more than what they are today used to. However, this may change in near future when market prices for WPCs become more competitive and volumes are growing to start causing logistics issues and increased pricing due longer transportation costs.

The global wood plastic composites market is driven by high availability of non-utilized plastic and wood and other natural fibre wastes, increase in demand from building & construction applications, and stringent regulations on the use of chemicals in building materials. However, rise in cost of raw materials and issues related to mechanical strength and/or weight hamper their potential for several structural applications. Conversely, increase in implementation of biodegradable raw materials is expected to create opportunities in the global WPC market. Market players have adopted merger as their key strategy to widen their brand portfolios and expand their market reach.

Rising application scope in decking and fencing applications is expected to drive demand for the product in the construction industry. Growing demand for wood plastic composite as a low cost and environment-friendly substitute to plastic and steel components in construction applications is expected to drive the market growth. Better recyclability, thermal stability, and stiffness offered by the wood plastic composites are expected to open new avenues for the industry growth over the next eight years. Moreover, rising application scope in street constructions and landscaping owing to the noise barrier properties offered by the product is likely to propel demand.

Though construction industry was affected by the overall global economic slowdown in 2014-2015, the demand for wood-plastic composites from the construction industry is

anticipated to increase in the coming years due to the superior performance benefits, durability, and low maintenance cost of these composites as compared to conventional materials. Growing demand for construction and automotive applications is expected to be a major driving force for the market, as well as growing demand for recyclable materials. The high cost of raw materials is a major restraint that may hamper market growth, but untapped markets in emerging countries are likely to open new opportunities.

Based on applications, building and construction accounted for more than 50% of the total market and this trend is likely to continue within the forecast period. Building & Construction segment is expected to remain the growth engine of the global WPC market during the forecast period. Decking, siding, and fencing are the major applications of WPC in the building & construction industry, together accounting for more than 90% of the WPC market in the building & construction industry in 2015.

The growth of the WPCs market is expected to happen at the expense of competing materials and innovation of new kinds of products for different end-uses. The main competitor for future markets of WPCs is wood, but there are also other competitive materials like biocomposites (including cellulose, and natural fiber reinforced polymers), vinyl, fibreglass reinforced plastics, concrete, and aluminium (Seppälä 2000, Principia Partners 2006).

In Europe, between 10 and 15% of the total composite market is covered by Wood-Plastic Composites (WPC) and Natural Fibre Composites (NFC), as it can be seen in Table 8.

Table 8. Wood-plastic and Natural-fibre Composites market

Biocomposites	Production in 2012	Forecast production in 2020 (without incentives for bio-based products)	Forecast production in 2020 (with strong incentives for bio-based products)
WPC			
Construction, extrusion	190,000 t	400,000 t	450,000 t
Automotive, compression moulding & extrusion/thermoforming	60,000 t	80,000 t	300,000 t
Technical applications, furniture and consumer goods, mainly injection moulding	15,000 t	100,000 t	> 200,000 t
<i>Traded granulates for extrusion and injection moulding</i>	<i>40,000 t</i>	<i>200,000 t</i>	<i>> 300,000 t</i>
NFC			
Automotive, compression moulding	90,000 t	120,000 t	350,000 t
Granulates, injection moulding	2,000 t	10,000 t	> 20,000 t

5.1.5 Other comments

The Landfill Directive sets the requirement that waste must be treated before being landfilled. The treatment requirement is specifically aimed at municipal biodegradable

waste (including also wood waste from construction). The Landfill Directive requires Member States to progressively reduce landfilling of municipal biodegradable waste to 35% by 2016 (compared to 1995). The objective of these measures is to reduce the production and release of greenhouse gases from landfills.

The ban for landfilling biodegradable waste (such as wood) has been implemented in different way in the European waste legislation. Several countries have introduced a limit for the organic content in the waste (e.g. by giving limits to the content of Total organic carbon).

5.2 Main challenges

In the building sector, the main challenge found by the participants was the durability of the products. This is because building products must last for very long periods, and they suffer the environmental consequences.

The summary of the most important challenges of the Building sector can be seen in Table 9.

Table 9. Summary of the most important challenges of the Building working group

Main Challenges Building	Materials	Products			
	Recycling	Remanufacturing	Refurbishing	Re-use	Long use
Dis-&re-assembly complexity	X		X	X	
Customer design expectations	X				
Mechanical requirements	X	X			X
Modularity complexity			X		
Mechanical recycling challenges					
Nonexistence market			X	X	
Material contamination					
Sorting challenges					
Economics		X			X
Durability challenges			X	X	X
Environmental challenges				X	X
Regulation limitations		X			X
Traceability control					
Adaptability issues					
Collection challenges					
People lack of awareness					

According to the questionnaire sent after the workshop, the main challenges found by the people who answered the questionnaire for the building sector were:

- *“Composites usually cannot be resurfaced, which is problematic for reuse strategies, for example, if the composite is scratched, damaged or changes colour when exposed to UV radiation. The reuse strategies could be also compromised by the way we join composites (e.g. drilling holes for bolts or screws).” (OUTDOOR PANELS)*

- *“The use of large fractions of recycled materials could impact the final products characteristics and compromise future circular strategies for product/part/materials” (OSB PANEL)*
- *“As it was “my product” the challenge I found was to get others to know and understand that a WPC-panel is easily recovered and recycled back in the same process BY ANY EXISTING WPC-PROFILE MANUFACTURER IN THE MARKET AND THEY WOULD HIGHLY APPRECIATE TO GET HOLD ON SUCH PRODUCTS IF FREE OF COSTS !” (OUTDOOR PANELS)*
- *“Find how we can remove plywood in existing buildings.” (PLYWOOD PANEL)*

5.3 Design solutions

These are the preferred design solutions selected by the participants of the workshop for the building sector. As it can be seen, the design solution most selected was the structural design. Table 10 shows the summary of the results. For more information, all results are collected in Annex I.

Table 10. Summary of the preferred design solutions for the Building working group

Design solutions Building	Materials	Products			
	Recycling	Remanufacturing	Refurbishing	Re-use	Long use
Dis-&re-assembly			X	X	
Modularity		X	X		
Identification					
Interchangeability					
Material selection	X				
surface treatment selection					X
Sorting					
Malfunction annunciation					X
Structural design	X	X	X	X	X
Fastener & connection selection				X	
Documentation					
Planning				X	
Simplify					X
Adaptability	X			X	
New business model					
Standardisation					
EU Regulations					

According to the questionnaire sent after the workshop, the main challenges found by the people who answered the questionnaire for the building sector were:

- *“Developing materials that will be of high-quality, scratch- or/and UV radiation-resistant. This of course adds costs to the material but technically feasible.” (OUTDOOR PANELS)*

- *“Designing new bolt- and screw-free joining methods that will not cause any mechanical damage to the composite (already in practice in the construction sector for wood components)” (OSB PANEL)*
- *“Mixing of natural and synthetic textile scraps for bi-components panels” (OUTDOOR PANELS)*
- *“Develop new Tools to remove those panels.” (PLYWOOD PANEL)*

Figure 5-1. The most important design solutions for the building sector according to the questionnaire results

5.4 Recovery strategies

Regarding the Building sector, Long use was chosen as the recovery strategy with more challenges to face, mainly due to the durability of the materials that need to fight against environmental conditions without losing their mechanical and aesthetic properties. Regulation also limits the use of building products for the long use, as long as they can suppose a problem for the safety.

On the other hand, the preferred recovery strategy, where more design solutions appeared, is Reuse. Participants best solutions include structural design, fastener and connection selection or adaptability, among other.

Figure 5-2. The most important design solutions for the furniture sector according to the product owner (questionnaire results)

Figure 5-3. The most important design solutions for the furniture sector according to the questionnaire average results

6 Extra information. Non-woven recovery (Input from Daniele Spinelli (NTT))

6.1 Recovery perspective

6.1.1 Design

In combination with other materials or used alone, nonwovens are used in a wide range of consumer and industrial products with diverse properties, including absorbent hygiene products, apparel, home furnishings, healthcare and surgical fabrics, construction, filtration, engineering, and wipes to name but a few.

They may be a limited life, single-use fabric or a very durable fabric. Nonwovens have specific characteristics that allow them to deliver high-performance across a wide range of applications. Specific functions include: absorbency, liquid repellence, resilience, stretch, softness, strength, flame retardancy, washability, cushioning, filtering, bacterial barrier and sterility.

6.1.2 Present situation

The use of raw materials for nonwovens is once more in a state of uncertainty. Petroleum – upon which polypropylene polymer and fibre, polyester polymer and fibre, bicomponent fibres, polyethylene polymer, and most binders depend upon directly – is now at a much lower price and higher supply than it has been for several years.

In theory, polymers and fibres used in nonwovens should be stable and lower in price. Actually, issues like refinery and spinning capacity, oil well and facility shutdowns (prompted by the low world prices), will continue to make nonwoven pricing and supply less certain.

There are many factors affecting the selection of raw materials for nonwovens, including process efficiency, product performance, and consumer demand; but in some cases, price is a determining factor.

6.1.3 Tools & machines

One way to categorise nonwovens is by their methods of manufacture. Nonwovens can be divided into three distinctive groups: those produced by dry-laid methods; wet-laid methods; or spun melt processes. One of the major advantages of nonwoven manufacture is the speed at which fabric can be produced, especially when compared to the production rates of knitted or woven fabrics. The effect of this process parameter is the reduction in the cost of manufacturing.

Dry-laid nonwovens

Dry-laid nonwovens are formed from staple fibres. These fibres are then processed to create fibrous webs which have little mechanical integrity. The webs are then bonded either by mechanical, thermal or chemical means. Sometimes a secondary bonding process will also be applied.

Air-laid technology produces a randomly orientated fibrous web

Airlaid short fibres of 1-15 mm and particles are dispersed in air by various means. A common method employs rotating blades, which produces a "cloud" of fibres within the airlay chamber. The fibres are then transported through the air toward a permeable conveyor belt under which suction is applied. This helps to gather the fibres onto the conveyor surface, where the web is formed.

Dry laid bonding methods

There are three different types of bonding, mechanical, thermal, and chemical. A variety of different processes come under these different headings.

Wet-laid nonwovens

The principle of wetlaying is similar to paper manufacturing. The difference lies in the amount of synthetic fibres present in a wetlaid nonwoven. A dilute slurry of water and fibres is deposited on a moving wire screen and drained to form a web. The web is further dewatered, consolidated, by pressing between rollers, and dried. Impregnation with binders is often included in a later stage of the process.

The strength of the random oriented web is rather similar in all directions in the plane of the fabric. A wide range of natural, mineral, synthetic and man-made fibres of varying lengths can be used.

Spunmelt nonwovens

In these processes, webs are made directly from filaments spun from plastics in liquid form.

Spunbond

Spunbond is the most direct method of making a nonwoven. Continuous filaments, not staple fibres, are spun (extruded) directly from polymer chip. Normally, polymers are melt-extruded in the spunbond process. The formation of a web of continuous filaments deposited on the conveyor belt is assisted by suction. The web is then bonded directly by various means, normally thermal bonding.

Meltblown

Meltblown is similar to spunbond but produces much finer filaments. The hot, molten, liquid polymer is forced through nozzles to form a stream of polymer. At the nozzle tip,

the filaments are picked up by hot, high velocity air streams that stretch the filaments by drag forces into very fine diameters. The filaments gradually cool as they travel across to the collector. The use of suction at the collector assists in web formation.

6.1.4 Changes in type of materials

The reference materials for nonwovens production are polypropylene and polyester as per OEM specs for automotive, furniture and building applications.

6.1.5 Other comments

In the past, there has been no simple technical solution for recycling non-woven process waste, which consists of side trim and reject rolls. They have been sent to landfill or in the best case incinerated for energy recovery. The objective is to investigate their re-manufacturing process demonstrating the use of a high recycled material percentage (up to 90%).

7 Extra information. Additional comments from the questionnaire

What should be improved on or added to these sets of strategies?

- *"It was OK. Very complete."*
- *"Eliminating environmental poisonous components"*
- *"Easy to recycle material to keep it in the loop as long as possible"*
- *"It could be important to cluster the strategies in some categories to facilitate the work of those not familiar with the design process by providing a kind of guided experience"*
- *"LCA and LCCA"*
- *"The final outlook of the furniture product have great impact on customer perception."*
- *"predictive knowledge of the life cycle of the parts (eg how much life does the part or system still have remaining?)"*
- *"Products, when designed, should have the circular strategy into account and, for each product, a value chain should be established."*

For which step in the design process would you like extra support?

- *"Choice of materials"*
- *"Identifying materials. Easiness to disassemble."*
- *"Identifying type of plastic with enough accuracy"*
- *"Most OEMs require support in the material selection"*

- *"choice of material, action and processes"*
- *"At the stage of developing the conceptual solution, it would be interesting to have a set of topics (maybe a checklist) to be considered in that conceptual design"*
- *"It could be also important to have some guidance on how to address material choice, product functionalities and integration of circular design strategies"*
- *"No. The idea is to use current available technologies."*
- *"comparing existing products and solutions dominantly in the market with the new product and reasoning in real business terms"*
- *"what possibly could prevent the new product entering the market and how design strategies could help to overcome this"*
- *"The optimum resin dosage parameters and its crucial properties that have to be taken into account"*
- *"material selection and evaluation methods"*
- *"How we can improve to collect at the end of life (organisation, transport...)"*
- *"No need for extra support"*

Are there specific design tools you would like to use?

- *"A cross plastic labelling and assembly- disassembly standardisation for all vehicles manufacturers"*
- *"Sensing and automatization"*
- *"Modular structure, easy dismantling, upgrading"*
- *"physically durable, easy to disassemble"*
- *"It would be then interesting to have a clear idea of the main steps of the design strategy and what kind of tools can be used at those stages"*
- *"It would be interesting to have a list of suggested tools for those stages (e.g. Material selection, CAD, LCA etc.)"*
- *"No."*
- *"design thinking"*
- *"no"*
- *"No."*

- *"Management and further development of time planning for disassembly process? (assembly time is known)"*
- *"Economic evaluation of a circular economy model"*
- *"Impact evaluation."*
- *"No"*

Do you have any other questions, remarks or recommendations?

- *"The workshop was fine and fun! Very interesting listening other stakeholders challenges."*
- *"No."*
- *"summary of building, furniture & automotive"*
- *"no :)"*
- *"The workshop was a great opportunity to start brainstorming about the potential products and some of the relevant considerations from the user point of view. We come up with some ideas and points to be discussed."*
- *"It could be interesting to have a better idea of the whole strategy, so people could have clear the relevance of each step and what it is expected to get from it."*
- *"No."*
- *"As the word "plastic waste" has got a very bad image lately, though it (thermoplastics) is a very good and easy material for recycling (but not thermosets), one should value the fact 1kg recycled thermoplastic in composites like WPCs is recycling 2kg other difficult to recycle waste materials into new life cycle and this is an undiscovered potential to become used in design strategies"*
- *"Thanks."*
- *"More engagement with and understanding of supply chain and their ambitions for their own circular economy"*
- *"No thanks."*
- *"Your method is very interesting !"*
- *"No"*

8 Design progress

The workshops and questionnaire delivered valuable insights in the challenges and opportunities for circular redesign of the reference products. These observations were used to compose individual redesign assignments for the manufacturing partners. The redesign approach has four sections:

- Product description: detailing the reference product and design requirements
- Challenges & problems: establishing two major concerns found in the workshops
- Design principles: Proposing design principles that can help solve the problems
- Application & effects: redesign of reference product & evaluation of result

Challenges & problems: For each reference products, two major concerns were identified from the workshop and questionnaire. In total, four main challenges were found:

Dis- & re-assembly	Removing the components from the product assembly and mounting them in a new product.
Physical durability	Withstanding degradation and ageing effects over the product's service lifes.
Emotional durability	Keeping the product desirable for the consumers, i.e. resisting changes in fashion and design appearance
Repair of material	Keeping the product functional requires maintenance or repairs, which can be enabled through careful design and material selection.

Design principles: The workshop & questionnaire also asked participants for design suggestions to address these challenges. The suggestions were categorised using the design strategy framework, and a shortlist of most design principles deemed most relevant was made, definitions of the listed principles can be found in section 2.3:

- Adaptability
- Interchangeability
- Modularisation
- Standardisation
- Surface treatment

Application: The manufacturers were asked to apply these design principles in their redesign and evaluate the results, reflecting on the initial challenges. The following subchapters provide a summary of the redesign progress. An extended description of the method is given in report D2.2 Design strategies & tools, V1. Extended information on reference products is given in report D2.1 Report on baseline description.

8.1 MAIER

The fascia is a component of the central console. It is made of several parts (frame, fascia and fasteners) assembled to the vehicle by snap-fits and screws.

Figure 8-1 MAIER reference product

Although it is designed as a structural support (electronic system, aerators, screens) the aesthetic finish is the main functionality. All the parts of the component are made of thermoplastic materials by injection moulding. Due to different aesthetic and technical requirements, most of the finishing surfaces are made by coating, painting or plating processes before the assembly operations.

Challenges & problems	For your product the two main challenges identified during the workshop are:
Dis- & re-assembly	Regulations dictate the component must be designed to allow the easy Dis+Re-Assembly operations for the maintenance operations and at the End of Life of the vehicle.
Physical durability	Withstanding degradation and ageing effects over the product's service lifes. The durability of the component depends mainly on the resistance (light, chemical, abrasion) of the aesthetic surface finishes. Reinforced and/or Recycled thermoplastic materials negatively affect the aesthetic finish of the painted parts with lack of adhesion, heterogeneity and reproducibility of colour and gloss.

Proposal of redesign of the component: integration of functions in a single part injected in two materials. Top side made of conventional thermoplastic compatible with coating/paint processes for the aesthetic finishes; Back side made of reinforced/recycled thermoplastic; fixations (snap-fits, clips) on back side get from the injection step.

Figure 8-2 MAIER product redesign

Effects	
Dis- & re-assembly	Easier Assembly/Disassembly operations due to the reduction of parts for a multi-functional component. Easier recycling operations due 2K parts made of fully compatible materials.
Physical durability	Possibility of aesthetic finishes based on natural, reinforced and/or recycled materials (Composite Aesthetics). Possibility of improving the use of recycled materials (on back side of the component).
Remaining hurdles	The performance of (recycled) Ecobulk materials: Processability (injection moulding), actual performance (mechanical, thermal, chemical), light stabilization and thermal aging, compatibility with finishing processes according to aesthetic specifications for automotive interior applications.

8.2 Microcab

Figure 8-3 Microcab product prototypes

Two car interior components are considered for redesign: dashboard cowlings and switchpack housing. The dashboard cowlings house the display and consists of multiple parts. The front surround of the main display is now clipped onto the aluminium support frame which holds the display. The rear portion of the cowling is then bolted through the back into the frame. This system is good for quick disassembly.

The switchpack cowling is similarly slipped over the switch bracket and screwed in place with self-tapping screws from behind (Fig. 11). As this part is continually touched by the driver whilst operating the switches it is subject to the most wear and tear, so will need to be refurbished more often than other parts.

Challenges & problems	For your product the two main challenges identified during the workshop are:
Dis- & re-assembly	There may be an issue with bolts that could be removed by the user in the 2 cases mentioned here. These may have to be covered with caps to prevent unwanted access by users or non-service personnel. We will have to look at time taken to build up these parts and systems as long build time will tend to raise costs of product.
Emotional durability	In terms of emotional durability, 'design for circularity' needs to develop its own language so that users become familiar with why things are styled in certain ways to allow for remanufacture.

The main thrust of the design process has been towards modularization of parts to allow replacement of small parts as and when necessary without having to 'scrap' large elements. The second most important consideration is that of surface treatment of the parts. Some of the materials which are coming through the Ecobulk project have quite interesting aesthetic qualities which may be suitable in the wider context of our vehicle interior designs. We will be trying to use the materials as they are (natural) without having to surface treat them (eg paint). This makes a positive statement about the material choice and does not try to disguise them and make them appear as something else.

Effects	Evaluation of redesign
Dis- & re-assembly	An improvement on the previous design which was very difficult to disassemble and required a lot of preparation and surface treatment

Emotional durability	This has to be tested with a user group, but the design team and other colleagues are pleased with the direction the design is taking.
Remaining hurdles	To identify Ecobulk materials for use & to examine the cost of the build process in detail.

8.3 Conenor

Figure 8-4 Conenor reference product examples

Composite solid board (multilayer) and panel (single layer) for outdoor use. Extruded thermoplastic composite board/panel consisting of;

- G-FRP waste from demolished wind turbine blades
- wood fibres from waste wood (pine)
- recycled HDPE- or PP-plastic from consumer packaging
- additives (processing aid, coupling agent, color pigment, mineral)

Challenges & problems	For your product the two main challenges identified during the workshop are:
Dis- & re-assembly	do not use nails but removable screws/bolts when necessary for fixing, avoid making holes unless needed for fasteners. do not cast in concrete or equal to create a hybrid structure
Repair of material	material is colored online at manufacturing and no need for painting which is not recommended either afterwards, gluing is possible but with limited effect with a selected type of glue.

Use "slotted assembly" where the product is fixed from the ends into a groove to avoid using any type of fasteners (see photo). use "pane type of roofing" with panels to avoid unnecessary fasteners nor use of sealants. material is designed to last several years in

outdoor use without the need of any maintenance or repair – if necessary; remove any broken materials from the assembly and replace with new ones and return the broken pieces back to manufacturer for re-manufacturing.

Figure 8-5 Conenor product redesign

8.4 Moretti

Moretti has chosen to redesign a bookcase. The bookcase is made of particleboard coated with melamine paper (or laminated for a higher resistance in time) F**** class, and finished with polypropylene edges. The idea is to experimentally introduce glass or aluminum replaceable covers in order to protect coatings during the whole life cycle (the same as for smartphone). If possible maintain the same manufacturing process. The next design should maintain the same aesthetic now used.

Figure 8-6 Reference product, furniture

Challenges & problems	For your product the two main challenges identified during the workshop are:
Dis- & re-assembly	Removing the components from the product assembly and mounting them in a new product.
Emotional durability	Withstanding degradation and ageing effects over the product's service lifes.

The redesign products are composed by two different typologies of cube and they can have different destination of use; the possibility of disassembly and re-assembly is guaranteed by the utilization of removeable screws and gluing systems. Under the design point of view, the company will adopt essential lines and shapes, so has to have pleasant appearance in time, and neutral colours such as scales of white and grey.

Figure 8-7 Redesign of Moretti Compact furniture

Effects	Evaluation of redesign
Dis- & re-assembly	There are no particular problems as the cubes will be connected to each other with simple systems that anyone can disassemble and reassemble. At the end of their life they can be recycled entirely, being made of wood particles, glue and PPL edges. Even in case of glass or aluminum covers, the product will be entirely recyclable. With aluminum, panel producers will have the possibility to macerate the products, thus obtaining particles in wood and aluminum: these latter will guarantee a higher resistance of new particleboard panels.
Emotional durability	The emotional durability will be related also to the Eco-sustainability of products and their non toxicity: one of the aim is to have 0 formaldehyde emission panels.
Key requirements	Recyclable materials, reusable components, utilization of elements suitable for disassembling and re-assembling (screws, glues), simple lines and shapes, neutral colours.
Remaining hurdles	None identified

9 References

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10 Annex I. Detailed workshop results (Confidential)

Table 11. Workshop Results AUTOMOTIVE G1

	AUTOMOTIVE- G1-CRF- Trim for central panel - CIRCULAR STRATEGIES				
	Felipe Maya (EXERGY), Ajith (CRANFIELD UNI), Mangino Enrico (CRF), Laura Moretta (GRANTA), Sara Gaultieri (TECHNOPLANTS), Francisco Saraiva (COVENTIVE),				
	Materials	Products			
	Recycling	Remanufacturing	Refurbishing	Re-use	Long use
Actions & Processes	- Incentives for end-user (owner of the vehicle) to give his car for parts recycling at the end of life of the vehicle, COVENTIVE				
Challenges	- How can we convince OEM's designers, part manufacturers and end users to implement the necessary changes?, COVENTIVE	- Possible to think on DIY solutions? Printing components at home for customization, EXERGY	- Aesthetic factors: color, touch - Mechanical performances: hard/soft - Durability: color loss, expected life span, GRANTA	- Changes come with the time (expecting something new), CRANFIELD - Color parts? Color covers to customized interior?, EXERGY	Durability, CRANFIELD
Design solutions	- New legislation forcing the single part recycling, CRF - Ensure safety/security of produced products, TECHNOPLANTS		- Balance aesthetic choices vs. New recycled materials choice. Can we change the color if the material can be applied to a variety of components?, GRANTA	- Design for disassembly (screws, reversible snapfits), CRF - Soft/easy/flexible to fix component made of one plastic (no clips), GRANTA - Structure made of linear components like truss structures so components could be re-used in other components, EXERGY	

Table 12. Workshop Results AUTOMOTIVE G2

	AUTOMOTIVE- G2-MICROCAB- CIRCULAR STRATEGIES				
	Dominik (EXERGY), Erna Muks (TECNARO), Solitario Nesti (NTT), John Jostin (MICROCAB)				
	Materials	Products			
	Recycling	Remanufacturing	Refurbishing	Re-use	Long use
Actions & Processes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mechanics delivery- broken pieces to remanufacturers getting incentive/payment instead of paying to residues management companies, EXERGY - Recycling textiles in thermoplastic components, NTT - Recyclable materials neat, less additives, TECNARO 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use recycled materials for structural parts, TECNARO 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reuse plastic with textile fibers for composites, NTT 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Coating as ceramic --> plasma treatment, TECNARO - Surface modification, TECNARO - Inner design time intervals for small parts (more efficiently) which can be changed/replaced with time. TECNARO - Polymers with good properties, mechanical resistance, TECNARO - Upgrading component (technological changes), EXERGY
Challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Blend mixture of materials, TECNARO 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Expensive to dismantle, MICROCAB 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Difficult to separate parts, MICROCAB 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Customer changing preferences on design, EXERGY 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mechanical properties, resistance, degradability of bio-polymers, TECNARO - Finding new aesthetics for circular economy, MICROCAB - Changing the screen without changing the whole component, EXERGY - Develop new function of composites, f.i. antibacterial activity, NTT
Design solutions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Simplify design, MICROCAB 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - New technology of textiles for reduce new material for automotive, NTT - Structure. One part out of one material by composite, TECNARO - Reduce number of materials use, MICROCAB 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Minimise fixings, don't use adhesives, MICROCAB 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - New use of textiles on components of automotive, NTT - Design for alternatives, second life, MICROCAB - Flexible structure, EXERGY 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Easy dismantling design, EXERGY - Collaborate with supplier to work on components, EXERGY

Table 13. Workshop Results AUTOMOTIVE G3

	AUTOMOTIVE- G3-MICROCAB- CIRCULAR STRATEGIES				
	Zaratiana (FCBA), Daniele (NTT), Oliver (TOMRA), Guillermo (IRIS),Olivia (OAKDENE), Sonia (AIMPLAS), Anne (MICROCAB)				
	Materials	Products			
	Recycling	Remanufacturing	Refurbishing	Re-use	Long use
Actions & Processes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cutting and mix with concrete or resine / glue (panel), FCBA - Improve agregability of materials before remanufacturing, IRIS <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Insulation panels, NTT - Material sorting from ASR, TOMRA <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Shredder and be part of other products, AIMPLAS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Termoforming of ABS residues with thermoplastics and natural fibers, NTT 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ability to remove smaller buttons or dials from console, OAKDENE <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - cutting, FCBA 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Decide which parts can be reused as they are and which ones need alternative strategies, OAKDENE 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Evaluate the shelf life of recycled products, IRIS
Challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mechanical characteristis, FCBA - Contamination of materials, MICROCAB - Material recovery not in place today for ASR, TOMRA <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - NIR-Detectable carbon black, TOMRA - Economics, costs, TOMRA 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Avoid the use of chemical compounds, IRIS - Effect on tooling (if applicable) of material choice, MICROCAB - Assembly for timber frame building, FCBA 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How they can be fixed so they don't drop off during use but come off easily and quickly during reman/refurbish? OAKDENE 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Aesthetic of material?, MICROCAB - Solutions for replacement parts?, MICROCAB - Ability to change visual appearance to meet change in fashions, OAKDENE 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How do the stakeholders that influence how the product is maintained, get value from longer life?, OAKDENE <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - lightweight material, NTT - Durability, TOMRA
Design solutions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - NIR-Detectable colour VS MIR (Middle infrared technology), TOMRA - Metal larger to separate it, AIMPLAS - Brick or panel for building, FCBA 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Initial design for reassembly, removal of individual parts, MICROCAB 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Plasma treatment on the surface of materials to enhance their adhesiveness to paints, IRIS - Create materials with inherent aesthetic properties, honest of materials! MICROCAB - Decoration and indoor design, FCBA 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Nesting of parts (console parts within dashboard parts), MICROCAB 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop new assembly, FCBA - Infrared materials -> conflict with recyclability?, TOMRA - Grade + categorise parts which are likely to have most wear tear, MICROCAB

Table 14. Workshop Results AUTOMOTIVE G4

		AUTOMOTIVE- G4-MAIER- CIRCULAR STRATEGIES				
		Joan Bellver(GBP metal group), Emilia Ferreres (GBP metal group), Eva Verdejo (Aimplas), Mario Ordonez (MAIER), Rachel Waugh (Oakdene Hollins), Jelle Joustra (TU Delft,				
		Materials	Products			
		Recycling	Remanufacturing	Refurbishing	Re-use	Long use
Actions & Processes	Disassembly, TU Delft				Customize the painting, GPB metal	
Challenges	<p>Compatibility of coatings with recycling process, TU Delft</p> <p>Money & cost, vs. Value of recovered material , TU Delft</p> <p>Emissions of dangerous substances, TU Delft</p> <p>ASR sorting on colors - plastics can have many colors, TU Delft</p> <p>Tools needed for disassembly, TU Delft</p> <p>Incentive/recovered value , TU Delft</p> <p>Use of compatible coating with polymeric material, Aimplas</p> <p>Use of compatible materials, Aimplas</p> <p>Development of cheaper compatibilizers, Aimplas</p> <p>Compatibility of materials in recycling process, MAIER</p> <p>Availability of recycled materials, MAIER</p> <p>Cost <€10/part makes maintenance uneconomic, MAIER</p> <p>Electronic elements & screens integrated , MAIER</p> <p>Multifunctional parts, MAIER</p> <p>UV degradation, MAIER</p> <p>Plastic replacement with new part is more economic than product re-use, MAIER</p>				Same assembly system along time & models, GBP	Long life part, GBP
Design solutions	<p>Composite not used on visual part, but for frame, MAIER</p> <p>Front fascia of ABS, with back structure of ABS+recycled composite, MAIER</p> <p>Reducing energy use by recycling, MAIER</p> <p>Good properties and purity of recycled materials to justify them</p> <p>Use markers for materials-facilitate separation, Aimplas</p> <p>Reduce OEM choice for materials, Oakdene Hollins</p> <p>(especially non-visual) integration of parts increases part weight, makes for more value per part, TU Delft</p>				<p>No polymer blends & limit the number of additives, Aimplas</p> <p>Deposit scheme for parts, Oakdene Hollins</p> <p>Transition to non-ICE vehicles, is it worth working on ICE ? , Oakdene Hollins</p> <p>Repair technologies (dents etc), Oakdene Hollins</p> <p>Change ELV directive (reuse targets, volume based, plastics specific), Oakdene Hollins</p> <p>Standardisation across OEMS (e.g. non visual components backing, Oakdene Hollins</p> <p>Reuse whole console, Oakdene Hollins</p> <p>Better UV coatings on glass to reduce ageing effects of UV, Oakdene Hollins</p> <p>Legislation to enforce recovery, TU Delft</p>	

Table 15. Workshop Results FURNITURE G1

FURNITURE- G1- BOOKCASE - CIRCULAR STRATEGIES					
Giovanni (Moretti), Dominik (Exergy), Alexandre (lipor), Emilie (FCBA), Enric (UPC), Markku (Conenor), Solitario (NTT), Jelle (TU Delft, facilitating)					
	Materials	Products			
	Recycling	Remanufacturing	Refurbishing	Re-use	Long use
Actions & Processes	using recycled wood in WPC's saves forest & lowers co2 footprint, conenor Recycle wood waste into composites, Conenor		Easy dismantle for replacing components, Exergy	Reuse old furniture for create new design models, Lipor Multifunctional design, Exergy	
Challenges	Chemical contaminants, Moretti New material instead of particle board: WPC, formaldehyde free, Conenor No WPC panel manufacturers in EU market, Conenor WPC from recycled particle board for moist conditions/winter resistant	Test the use of plastic+wood, for develop other characteristics for the materials, lipor Develop more options with modular system, to create new options for consumer, Lipor	Identification of origin & properties, UPC joinings for easy dismantling, Exergy Prepare a net of locals for repairing small damages in the materials, Lipor	Suitability for different uses, Moretti Performance of particle board with recycled vs virgin wood, FCBA Attractive design to customers of a furniture for multiple uses, Exergy Use of blocks in the structure of a building, FCBA	Mechanical properties: durability & resistance, Moretti Free formaldehyde binding, FCBA Produce furniture with textile panel, NTT Strengthening with biomolecules, FCBA Aesthetic features may not be accepted by customer, exergy
Design solutions		Attractive modular design for the consumer buy it, lipor Environmental advantages, lipor	Reinforce mechanical propeties with connections, FCBA develop joining solutions not compromising durability of a product, Exergy	Unique Design, Exergy	Resistent particle board (thickness), FCBA New function of material, NTT Increase security and reduce pollution in bedroom with the use of new material, NTT Single unit with multiple uses, Moretti Increase properties of of panel wood with textile fibre, NTT Looking for alternative materials, Exergy Inform user of bad use, FCBA

Table 16. Workshop Results FURNITURE G2

	FURNITURE- G2- BOOKCASE - CIRCULAR STRATEGIES				
	Felipe (EXERGY), Sara (TECHNOPLANTS), Hüseyin (KEAS), Rachel (OAKDENE HOLLINS), Zaratiana (FCBA)				
	Materials	Products			
	Recycling	Remanufacturing	Refurbishing	Re-use	Long use
Actions & Processes	- Use of extruded components for the basic cubes, EXERGY		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Repairing strategies favouring parts replacement and upgrades, EXERGY - Remove panel elements for another furnitures, FCBA - Use componible parts that can be modify for creating a new part of another piece of furniture, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Evolutive structures/products, EXERGY - Use as a wall (Mobile wall or insulated wall), FCBA 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Second-life for products in other industries, EXERGY - Customization of the components? Color, texture..., EXERGY - Stronger wood based panels, KEAS - Rent furniture, FCBA
Challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Panel manufacturing - particle board, FCBA - It is not easy to collect bulky wood waste for panel manufacturers, KEAS 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Should be clean. People don't want used furnitures, KEAS - Modularity challenge, dimensional lock in, OAKDENE - Is it possible to change color of the product with changing trends?, KEAS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Wear and tear affecting aesthetics, OAKDENE - Customer requirements changing over time (moving house), OAKDENE - Avoid downgrading applications, EXERGY - New assembly for evolutive furniture, FCBA
Design solutions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use particle board which can be recycled easily (eg. Some surface finishings can't be recycled), KEAS - Lease the furniture. Collect it back. New business model, KEAS 	No glue, OAKDENE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Customer repair kits, OAKDENE - Different design solutions for different customers (eg. Kids --> durable, students --> refurbish), OAKDENE 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use a fast and easy design for assembly and disassembly- in an automatic way, TECHNOPLANTS - Add insulation, FCBA - Dismounting elements that can't be combined in a wall, FCBA 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - High degree of customization so user becomes attached, OAKDENE - Make it easy for customers to return at end-of-life --> info attached to product, OAKDENE - Improve chemical and mechanical, FCBA - Buy back scheme/trade, OAKDENE - Covers, paint, EXERGY - Dye solution for spare parts, EXERGY

Table 17. Workshop Results FURNITURE G3

FURNITURE- G3- BOOKCASE - CIRCULAR STRATEGIES					
Oliver Lambert (TOMRA), Richard (AKZO NOBEL ADHESIVES), Diana Nicolau (LIPOR), Laura (GRANTA), Daniele (NTT), Olivia Bertham (OAKDENE HOLLINS), Yoann Montenot (FCBA), Cris (KNEIA)					
	Materials	Products			
	Recycling	Remanufacturing	Refurbishing	Re-use	Long use
Actions & Processes	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Design for recycling, thinking in the end-use, LIPOR Recovery of particle board/wood from bulky waste, TOMRA 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Formaldehyde emission from reused/recycled particle boards, AKZO Wood fibers reinforcement of bio-based plastics, NTT Mixed of synthetic thermoplastic fibers bonded to bio-based blenders, NTT 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Make it easy to desassembly, FCBA Eliminate need of screws, GRANTA 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Insulation panels, NTT For rent, OAKDENA Same materials from production instead of different materials to promote the possibility of re-use, LIPOR Make a partnership with an online retailer (f.i. leboncoin.fr), FCBA 	To get product back to recover materials, OAKDENA
Challenges	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Surface preparation- Fire resistance aesthetic factors, GRANTA Separate different materials (NIR), TOMRA 	Increase formaldehyde of emission reused/recycled particle boards, AKZO		<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Ease of storage if rented to institutions (university), OAKDENA People awareness (re-use instead of buying a new one), LIPOR Technical procedures to ensure and guarantee the re-use, LIPOR 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> If you (Moretti) don't own the product anymore, how do you get it back, OAKDENA Stabile and water resistant adhesive without formaldehyde emission, AKZO
Design solutions	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Estimate the market fo secondary raw materials, LIPOR Can be old children toys be used as a raw material?, OAKDENA HOLLINS New input material in particle board industry, TOMRA 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Formaldehyde scavenger in adhesives, AKZO Don't use formaldehyde, AKZO 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Replaceable panels for the section damaged, OAKDENA HOLLINS New assembly methods (Lego style), GRANTA Develop a system to disassemble without screws or tools, FCBA 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Public procurement by institutions buying big quantities: Elderly residences for example. Conditions for selection could include eco-criteria related with the product, KNEIA Beautiful/nice design, LIPOR Awareness campaigns to stimulate re-use, LIPOR Give information on the product (where to sell it when you don't need it anymore), FCBA 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Fashion concerns related with long use: searching possibilities for the final user for customization over and over again?, KNEIA Use solid wood to replace particled board, FCBA Choose materials according to mechanical performances, GRANTA Incentives to get products back (what value in materias!? More value in recyclable material than current), OAKDENA

Table 18. Workshop Results BUILDING G1

	BUILDING-G1- CONENOR PANELS- CIRCULAR STRATEGIES				
	Felipe (Exergy), Alexandre (Lipor), Emilie (FCBA), Dominik (Exergy), Solitario (NTT), Laura (Granta), Markku (Conenor), Jelle (TU Delft, facilitating)				
	Materials	Products			
	Recycling	Remanufacturing	Refurbishing	Re-use	Long use
Actions & Processes	Recycle OSB in conenor panel (FCBA) Surface preparation, Granta			Easy dismantling, Exergy Screwless connections, Granta	New concept for construction using photocatalic material, NTT Evolutive structures, Felipe Renting components for temporary structures, Felipe
Challenges	New material for reduce pollution indoor and increase quality of life, NTT	New composite, textile based, NTT Relatoin with municipal was collection, for use plastics at a lower price, Lipor Screw types to use for this material? Conenor	Use intelligent material for new concept of construction, NTT How to repair/resurface the material? TU delft Graffiti protection, Felipe/Exergy	Sowing solutions that makes damage to the panel, Dominik/Exergy Building blocks for construction, Felipe/Exergy Scratch resistivity, TU Delft	Impossible to resurface, Dominik Mechanical performances+regulations+safety, Granta Water poles for boats, Oysters, FCBA Heavy weight (density~1.3) an opportunity? TU Delft Price: more expensive than OSB, TU Delft Regulations & building codes apply for surface areas > 10 m2, Conenor Try to formulate a partnership with a company that commercializes garden material, Lipor
Design solutions	Multilayer extrusion, using WTB waste in the core of the extruded profile, Conenor		Heavy blocks for street security (terrorist attack), FCBA	Screw & bolts free joining solutions, Dominik Extrude base-shape (cillinder or hollow beam) for waste bin Service associated: embossing to give value (texturing), FCBA Reusable floor panels for exhibitions, FCBA	Children playgrounds, Lipor Automotive industry cargo areas, Lipor garden & outdoor equipment, lipor additives to make the panel more scratch resistant, dominik 3D shapes, FCBA Demonstrate: no biocides, toxins & formaldehyde free, TU Delft Fire retardancy, TU Delft

Table 19. Workshop Results BUILDING G2

	BUILDING-G2- OSB- CIRCULAR STRATEGIES				
	Rachel (OAKDENE HOLLINS), David (IRIS), Hüseyin (KEAS), Zaratiana (FCBA), Sara (TECHNOPLANTS)				
	Materials	Products			
	Recycling	Remanufacturing	Refurbishing	Re-use	Long use
Actions & Processes	- Virgin wood more expensive than waste for particle board, IRIS			- Longer life, KEAS	- Fire retardant, KEAS - More propriety for more durability (f.i. vapour barrier), FCBA
Challenges	- How measure quality requirements for end-users?, IRIS - Use less number of layers in wall in order to make disassembling easier, FCBA	- Too cheap (economic incentive/viability?), IRIS	- How are boards attached to each other /other building componens?, OAKDENE	- Finding non-structural applications for used OSB panels, OAKDENE - Packaging, FCBA - Furnitures, FCBA	- Increase the durability avoiding the humidity problem, TECHNOPLANTS - Durability?, IRIS -Warranty currently limited to 10 years, OAKDENE - Demonstrating properties after 10 years, OAKDENE
Design solutions				- Assembly that does not involve adding holes, OAKDENE - New assembly for easier removal, FCBA	- Add extra layer to prevent moisture ingress, OAKDENE - Humidity monitoring, OAKDENE - We can increase acoustic insulation, KEAS

Table 20. Workshop Results BUILDING G3

BUILDING-G3-PLYWOOD-FCBA CIRCULAR STRATEGIES					
Participants: Oliver(TOMRA), Daniele (NTT), Yoann Montenet (FCBA), Diana Nicolau (LIPOR), Olivia Bertham (OAKDENE HOLLINS), Richard (AKZO NOBEL ADHESIVE)					
Materials		Products			
Recycling	Remanufacturing	Refurbishing	Re-use	Long use	
Actions & Processes	Recovery from bulky waste, TOMRA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Define the material granules dimension according to specific functions of the final materials, NTT - Use as raw material as veneer production, AKZO NOBEL ADHESIVES 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Disassembly and cut panels to keep only good parts, FCBA 	-	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Synergies/Consortium with innovation centers, to expand the durable/consistency, etc, LIPOR
Challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To know qualities needed for different applications, TOMRA 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use of wet glue, AKZO NOVEL ADHESIVES 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Create a special stock market of recycling panels, FCBA 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Question the need to re-use wood products. Is a short carbon cycle a problem, what does LCA say?, OAKDENE HOLLINS - New process of disassembly --> New tools, FCBA 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Consider shorter life --> would need less environmental damaging adhesives? Would an easy to disassemble 5 year product be better?, OAKDENE HOLLINS - Moisture and mechanical stability, TOMRA - After 5 years change panels to change the disposition of rooms, FCBA
Design solutions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Look for biomimicry solutions for adhesives (f.i. what makes spider webs sticky?), OAKDENE HOLLINS - Closed loop recycling, TOMRA 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - New panels, mix plywood and OSB or particle boards, FCBA - Wood fibers with mixed textile scraps to produce insulation panels (non-woven production by air-laid technology), NTT - More modularization to exclude only the parts that must be substituted, LIPOR 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop specific assembly systems to facilitate disassembly, FCBA - Disassembly system without metal, FCBA - Could the panel be changed as part of maintenance? (do don't have to repaint,etc.), OAKDENE HOLLINS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use the damage material for interior design-decoration, LIPOR - Can magnets be used to hold layers in place rather than screws?, OAKDENE HOLLINS - Need to consider the whole frame structure to consider disassembly, OAKDENE HOLLINS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Add a water resistant coating that is not environmental damaging, OAKDENE HOLLINS * - Add a protection for external use, FCBA *